

VALKYRIES

D7.1 Testbeds and Evaluation Methodology

Reference Number: D7.1

Ed/Rev: A/0

Main Contributor: KEMEA

**Other Contributors: BC2050, BDI, BRC, HESE, HRT, INDRA,
ISEMI, PARTICLE, SERMAS, UMU, USN**

Date: 29/07/2022

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101020676

Editors

Name	Contact	Entity
John Tsaloukidis	j.tsaloukidis@kemea-research.gr	KEMEA
Danai Kazantzidou-Firtinidou	d.kazantzidou@kemea-research.gr	KEMEA
Georgios Sakkas	g.sakkas@kemea-research.gr	KEMEA

Contributors

Name	Entity	Contribution
Rumen Daton Medenou	INDRA	Testbed section, Verification section
Pedro Miguel Marco Manso Barbara Guerra	PARTICLE	Model Testbed and simulated actors, UC1, Integration with SIGRUN
Andrea Comelli	AREU	UC2 Review
Martin Kostolný	ISEMI	6.5.2 UC2
Sergio López Bernal	UMU	Review and feedback for sections 5, 6.4 and 6.5.1.
Maya Bozhilova Yantsislav Yanakiev	BDI	Review and feedback (sections 5.1, 6.5.3, 7.2), Review of section 6.5.3
Dimitrios Iliadis Iosif Vourvachis	HRT	UC3 general contribution, review of chapters 6 and 7
Miguel Gaspar	HESE	Reviewing
Nicolás Riera López Navid Behzadi Koochani	SERMAS	UC1 Review, general review of the document
Konstantinos Tsiomos Enrit Metai	BC2050	Development of the Testbed

Document Changes Record

Edit./Rev.	Date	Chapters	Reason for change
A/0	01/04/2022	All	Original Document

Content

1.	Executive Summary	1
2.	Identification	2
3.	Introduction	3
4.	Terminology and definitions	5
5.	Testbed	6
5.1.	Virtual Lab and Testbed	6
5.1.1.	Software elements	7
5.1.2.	Hardware elements	8
5.1.3.	Other elements	9
5.2.	Development of the Testbed	10
5.2.1.	Overview	10
5.2.2.	Gaps and Opportunities Registry	16
5.2.3.	Machine Communications Module: Machine to Machine (M2M) Messaging	16
5.2.4.	Audit Module	16
5.2.5.	Relation of TESTBED to SIGRUN INTEGRATION	16
5.2.6.	Setup	18
5.2.6.1	Code Repository	18
5.2.6.2	Kubernetes Cluster Overview	18
5.2.6.3	Connect to Azure VPN	19
5.2.6.3.1	Windows	20
5.2.6.3.2	MacOS/GNU-Linux	22
5.2.6.4	Daily Operation	22
5.2.7	First version of the demonstration of the Testbed	25
6	Testing strategy	26
6.1	Deployment of use cases in Exercise-Trials	26
6.2	Participants and Roles in an Exercise-Trial	26
6.3	The phases of an Exercise-Trial	28
6.4	Testbed and use cases	32
6.5	Use cases and key requirements	32
6.5.1	Use case 1 Spain-Portugal	33
6.5.2	Use case 2 Slovakia-Italy	35
6.5.3	Use case 3 Bulgaria-Greece	38
6.5.4	Use case 4 Norway-Denmark-The Netherlands	41

7	Evaluation Methodology	44
7.1	Definition of the term “Evaluation”	44
7.2	Definition of the terms “Verification” and “Validation”	45
7.3	Verification and Validation general flow	47
7.3.1	Verification of the harmonisation opportunities	49
7.3.2	Qualification Methods for Verification	52
7.3.3	Validation of the harmonisation opportunities	54
7.4	Evaluation criteria for achieving interoperability	57
8	Conclusions	59
9	Annex A - References and bibliography	60
10	Annex B - Glossary	61
11	Annex C – Indicative Questionnaires for Validation	62
12	Annex D – Indicative Questionnaire for the End User Technical Validation	63
13	Annex E - Indicative Table for the Results of Verification Tests	64

List of Tables

Table 1 - UC1 Actors and Technological Artefacts Mapping (Source: D2.3)	33
Table 2 - UC1 information flow (Source D2.3)	34
Table 3 - UC2 Actors and Technological Artefacts Mapping (Source D2.3)	35
Table 4 - UC2 Information Flows (Source D2.3)	36
Table 5 - UC3 Actors and Technological Artefacts Mapping (Source D2.3)	39
Table 6 - UC3 information flow (Source D2.3)	40
Table 7 - UC4 Actors and Technological Artefacts Mapping (Source D2.3)	42
Table 8 - UC4 information flow (Source D2.3)	43
Table 9 - Verification and Validation Plan	48
Table 10 – WP4 Harmonization opportunity potential tables	50
Table 11 – WP5 Harmonization opportunity potential tables	51
Table 12 – WP6 Harmonization opportunity potential tables	52
Table 13 - Glossary	61
Table 14 – Indicative questionnaires for validation	62
Table 15 – Indicative questionnaire for the end user technical validation	63
Table 16 – Indicative table for the results of verification tests	64

List of Figures

Figure 1 - Github Code Repository	7
Figure 2 - Gitflow Methodology	8
Figure 3 - AKS Kubernetes Infrastructure	8
Figure 4 - Harbor repository	9
Figure 5 - Testbed Overall Architecture	11
Figure 6 - Valkyries high-level framework concept (source deliverable D2.3)	11
Figure 7 - Testbed Data Flow (Data Broker Producer/Consumer Communication Model)	12

Doc title: Landscape of emerging preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters

Figure 8 - OpenAPI Development Pattern	13
Figure 9 - Testbed data source	15
Figure 10 - Test and validation framework.....	17
Figure 11: Screenshot from INDRA's github, source: https://github.com/DigitalLabsIndra/VALKYRIES_TESTBED	18
Figure 12: Azure VPN config files Download page	19
Figure 13: Azure VPN config files Download page	20
Figure 14: Azure VPN XML Config file.....	20
Figure 15: Azure VPN XML Config file.....	20
Figure 16: Azure VPN XML Config file.....	21
Figure 17: Azure VPN XML Config file.....	21
Figure 18: Connect to Azure VPN on Windows	22
Figure 19: Disconnect from Azure VPN on Windows	22
Figure 20: Azure VPN OpenVPN files.....	22
Figure 21: If working, OpenVPN should stay open	22
Figure 22: VALKYRIES Testbed Kubernetes Services Overview	23
Figure 23: VALKYRIES Testbed Kubernetes MQTT Overview	23
Figure 24: VALKYRIES Testbed Kubernetes Kibana Overview	24
Figure 25: Azure VPN Connection	24
Figure 26: Subscribing to a topic, in MQTT.....	24
Figure 27: Publishing a Short message tagged with a topic	24
Figure 28: ELK Web Interface	25
Figure 29 - Exercise-trial cycle	28
Figure 30 - UC2: Interaction Diagram on the side of Slovak Republic.....	37
Figure 31 - UC2: Interaction Diagram on the side of Italian Republic	38
Figure 32 - UC3: interaction Diagram (Source D2.3)	41
Figure 33 - UC4: Interaction Diagram (Source D.2.3).	43

1. Executive Summary

This document describes the development and the conceptual design of the Testbed and the system which will be used in the four use cases of the Valkyries project as well as the methodology for the technical verification and the end users' validation of harmonisation opportunities, which will be identified under the framework of the different Work Packages of the Valkyries project. Modules and services of the Testbed are described and provide insight and details regarding the way that systems from various organisations will be incorporated into the Testbed. Moreover, the organisation of trials (i.e., *validation of solutions by practitioners in the context of realistic situations and operational environment*) as exercises for the testing and evaluation of the harmonisation opportunities for the different use cases is detailed. Specifications regarding the phases of exercises, the participants and their roles are provided. In addition, the document provides a generic overview of the use cases with their functionalities and requirements, building upon previous deliverables, so as to depict the linkage between the specificities and the requirements of the use cases and the modules of the Testbed platform.

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Testbeds and Evaluation Methodology

Deliverable Id: D.7.1

Deliverable Title Abbreviation: D.7.1

Name of lead participant: KEMEA

Name of Contributors: BC2050, BDI, BRC, HESE, HRT, IND, ISEMI, PARTICLE, SERMAS, UMU, USN,

Type: Report (R) and Demonstrator (DEM)

Dissemination Level: Public (PU)

Proposed Classification Level: Non-Restricted

Reporting Conditions: Funding Requirement (FR)

Linked project Work Package: WP7 “Reference Integration, Evaluation and Demonstration”

Linked project tasks: T.7.1 “Testbeds and evaluation methodology”

Action: Design

Status: First Release

Document Layout: Custom layout

Details: This document describes the development of the Testbed and of the platform that will be used to test the harmonisation opportunities identified in WP4, WP5 and WP6. The modules and services that will be incorporated in the system are described. Moreover, the evaluation methodology that will be followed for the verification and validation of harmonisation opportunities is also provided in this document. Potential further modules for the platform and specifications for the evaluation methodology will be described in future deliverables of Tasks 7.3 “Reference Integration and harmonisations” and 7.4 “Evaluation and validation”.

3. Introduction

The main scope of the Valkyries project is to facilitate interoperability between end users in first aid response in case of multi casualty incidents. Interoperability, whether technological or procedural, is the main challenge, which has to be addressed by organisations not only at a national, but also at an EU and international level. The lack of interoperability in terms of common understanding and situational awareness, that is observed in emergencies which require collaboration of different organisations, is one of the most important factors of ineffectiveness in disaster management. The ambition of Valkyries is to map the landscape in terms of technology, operational procedures and education and cross-organisation collaboration, to identify gaps in these three domains and to provide harmonisation opportunities i.e., technologies, standards and standard operational procedures, training methodologies and educational material, which can be commonly adopted by first responders and used in their operations.

Deliverable 7.1 “Testbeds and Evaluation Methodology” is developed under the framework of the Task 7.1 of the same title. The Deliverable is built upon two main pillars, a) the conceptual design, development and demonstration of the Testbed and, consequently, of the technological platform, which will be used in the use cases and in which harmonisation opportunities, identified in WP4 “Equipment and ICT enablers for First Aid Responses”, WP5 “Common Practices and operational procedures for First Aid Responses” and WP6 “Cooperation, Education and Training for First Aid Responses” will be integrated and implemented, and b) the development of an evaluation methodology, which will be used for the technical verification and the end users’ driven validation of the system and of the harmonisation opportunities. The document comprises of three basic sections:

1. Section 5 “Testbed” describes the development of the Testbed and of the technical platform, that will be used in the use cases. Definitions of the terms “Testbed” and “virtual lab” are provided, as well as, an analytical description of the modules and services, of which the system is consisted, and of their functionalities. Furthermore, details regarding the integration of different systems into the platform are provided with the addition also of schematic representations.
2. Section 6 “Testing strategy”, in which the basic procedures that take place prior to, during and after an exercise are presented. An analysis regarding the phases of the exercise, the main participants, as well as the roles and responsibilities of the exercise management team are described. In addition, this section provides the reader with a general overview of the four use cases, the information flows and the interactions between the participants that will take place during the exercises.
3. Section 7 “Evaluation methodology” is dedicated, as its title suggests, to the development of a methodology which will be used for the evaluation of the technological and operational harmonisation opportunities. More specifically, regarding the technological aspect, the evaluation methodology is twofold, including the technical verification of the systems and tools, which will be undertaken by technological partners and experts of the consortium, and the validation of these technological solutions by the end users, who, in the context of the project, are the first responders.

The current document provides a first and more generic approach of the Testbed and the evaluation methodology taking into consideration that harmonisation opportunities have not yet been identified with the same applying to the definition of all the potential modules and

services, which will be integrated within the platform. Specificities and details regarding both the system and the performance indicators and metrics for the evaluation of opportunities will be defined in future deliverables relevant to Tasks 7.3 “Reference Integration and harmonisations” and 7.4 “Evaluation and validation”.

4. Terminology and definitions

The following terms have been defined with more details throughout the following chapters and are enlisted herein for the facilitation of the reader.

Evaluation is a systematic process that compares the result of measurement to recognized criteria to determine the discrepancies between intended and actual performance (ISO 22300:2021).

Exercise is the process to train for, assess, practice and improve performance in an organization (ISO 22398:2013).

Harmonisation opportunity is a technological solution or an operational procedure or educational material or a cross-organisation collaboration procedure which can be commonly adopted and used by end users for first aid response in multi casualty incidents.

Solution is a means that contributes to a crisis management function (CWA 17514).

Testbed is a platform for testing development projects. Testbeds generally involve rigorous, transparent and replicable testing of, for example, scientific theories, computational tools and new technologies (International Maritime Organization, 2014).

Trial is an event for systematically assessing solutions for current and emerging needs in such a way, that practitioners can do this, following a pragmatic and systematic approach (CWA 17514).

Validation is the process of evaluating a system or component during or at the end of the development process to determine whether it satisfies specified requirements (IEEE 1012:2016).

Verification is the process of providing objective evidence that the system, software or hardware and its associated products conform to requirements (e.g., for correctness, completeness, consistency and accuracy) for all life cycle activities during each life cycle process (acquisition, supply, development, operation and maintenance) (IEEE 1012:2016).

Virtual Lab is a technological platform which is, in its core, a controllable, collaborative, maintainable and operable work environment.

5. Testbed

In this chapter the conceptual design and development of the Valkyries Testbed is described. The different modules and services incorporated in the system are presented, as well as the basic steps to be followed for its setup. Additionally, screenshots are included and a demonstration video is developed to provide an overview and assist the reader in understanding the structure of the Testbed.

5.1. Virtual Lab and Testbed

A **Virtual Lab** is a technological platform which is, in its core, a controllable, collaborative, maintainable, distributed and operable work environment. As for projects such as Valkyries, collaboration may be done through online edition of documental artefacts - such as scenarios, deliverables, source code - a Virtual Lab is made of essentially a Testbed, coupled to services such as Identity Management, Access Management, or Documental Repository.

A **Testbed** is the core of a Virtual Lab, it is the only essential component. There are various definitions of the term "Testbed".

According to the Maritime Safety Committee of the International Maritime Organization "A *testbed (also commonly spelled as "test bed" in research publications) is a platform for trialling development projects. Testbeds generally involve rigorous, transparent and replicable testing of, for example, scientific theories, computational tools and new technologies*". Pospisil et al. (2021) consider the testbed as "a platform that simulates real-world activities under supervision. Testbeds are mainly used for experimental activities and to verify the results of these activities".

The Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation, which is an Australian Governmental agency for scientific research defines testbed as "a platform for conducting rigorous, transparent, and replicable testing of scientific theories, computational tools, and new technologies. The term is used across many disciplines to describe experimental research and new product development platforms and environments".

Fortier and Michel (2003) describe that "testbeds are composite abstractions of systems and are used to study system components and interactions to gain further insight into the essence of the real system. They are built of prototypes and pieces of real system components and are used to provide insight into the workings of an element(s) of a system. The important feature of a testbed is that it only focuses on a subset of the total system. That is, the important aspect that we wish to study, refine, or develop is the aspect implemented in the testbed. All other aspects have stubs that provide their stimulus or extract their load but are not themselves complete components, just simulated pieces. The testbed provides a realistic enough hardware-software environment with which to test components without having the ultimate system. The testbed provides means to improve the understanding of the functional requirements and operational behavior of the system. It supplies measurements from which quantitative results about the system can be derived. It provides an integrated environment in which the interrelationships of solutions to system problems can be evaluated."

It is apparent that various definitions of the term exist but all of them converge to the fact that **a Testbed is an environment used for the examination and testing of activities, procedures, and technologies.**

The following subchapters describe the functions and components that will be incorporated in the Testbed of the Valkyries project.

A suitable environment will be established, controlled, and maintained to carry out the software engineering effort required by the project, which will allow development teams to have a stable environment to be able to achieve their milestones and objectives iteratively. The environment aims to apply the paradigm and techniques of continuous development/integration, ensuring that integration between the different parts can be tested early and continuously. The set of tools and frameworks allow to create a common infrastructure that can enable:

- an open development platform
- uniformity and consistency of the artefacts developed
- deployment and unit testing on intermediate artefacts
- on-demand integration testing
- assess the progress and quality of the tests and results obtained
- support for verification and validation of the entire software system

5.1.1. Software elements

The screenshot shows a GitHub repository page for 'DigitalLabsIndra / VALKYRIES_TESTBED'. The repository is private. It features a navigation bar with options like 'Code', 'Issues', 'Pull requests', 'Actions', 'Projects', 'Security', 'Insights', and 'Settings'. Below the navigation, there are buttons for 'Go to file', 'Add file', and 'Code'. A recent merge pull request #2 is highlighted, showing 12 commits. A file list table is visible with columns for file name, commit message, and time since last commit. The 'About' section on the right indicates 'No description', 'GPL-3.0 license', '0 stars', '1 watch', and '0 forks'. A 'Releases' section is also present at the bottom.

File	Commit Message	Time
README	Update README1.txt	6 days ago
environment	yaml varios	28 days ago
LICENSE	Initial commit	last month

Figure 1 - Github Code Repository¹

Testbed software is a software product developed through CD (Continuous Delivery) process, which enables to store the code of the product on code repositories, in this case a private Github Repository¹. CD process is coupled to a Gitflow branching development methodology.

¹ https://github.com/DigitalLabsIndra/VALKYRIES_TESTBED/

Figure 2 - Gitflow Methodology

5.1.2. Hardware elements

Figure 3 - AKS Kubernetes Infrastructure

Aforementioned CD (Continuous Delivery) approach enables a swifter deployment into the cloud provider.

The Valkyries Testbed is intended to run inside a Kubernetes Cluster. A Kubernetes Cluster is a set of hardware infrastructure which runs a Kubernetes virtual environment. Since Kubernetes provides an additional layer of abstraction on top of the hardware layer, the Testbed is hardware agnostic. In that direction, the Testbed is codified as an IaC (Infrastructure as a Code) so it can be executed in any private or public cloud infrastructure, hopefully without too much personalisation.

There are two Kubernetes namespaces (independent machine environments): Valkyries-dev and Valkyries-pre, as in “development” and “pre-production”. Valkyries-dev hosts instances yet in development and Valkyries-pre namespace contains a stable replica of the Testbed, which is not so often updated, but contains stable releases. A Kubernetes Ingress module allows access to both environments seamlessly without the one interfering with the other, through Kubernetes Namespaces. A ‘Kubernetes Ingress’ is the Kubernetes equivalent of a Reverse Proxy. A reverse proxy is a web frontend which allows to translate IP and Ports into domain and subdomain names. It enables a DNS and FQDN access architecture to services, thus enabling easier swapping and or plugging of components, and even changing IP and ports without affecting user experience.

In addition to the Kubernetes containers, other applications or services are supported by the Testbed that run in a so called “native” mode (non-Kubernetes). Herein, components are deployed in a compatible environment inside the Valkyries Testbed, seamlessly interacting with other components (including those in the Kubernetes cluster), following the Valkyries interoperability framework (VIF), as described in chapter 5.2.

5.1.3. Other elements

Azure Kubernetes Service (AKS) has several auxiliary services such as Identity Server, VPN server. These are not strictly necessary in order to instantiate the Testbed.

Nevertheless, it is a good practice to have a Docker Registry (or Harbor Registry), which, in this case, is provided by INDRA.

Figure 4 - Harbor repository²

² https://docksdtr.indra.es/account/sign-in?redirect_url=%2Fharbor%2Fprojects

5.2. Development of the Testbed

In the framework of the Valkyries project the development of a Testbed is foreseen. This Testbed shall consist of several technological modules or components, which will facilitate the implementation of procedures aiming at covering the requirements that are set by the end users of the Consortium and at harmonising gaps in first aid response. Four use cases are planned to be executed via trials under the framework of WP7, in which the developed Testbed will support the testing and validation of the harmonisation opportunities achieved by the integration of different systems and services. This Testbed will provide a common infrastructure to be used for all the use cases and their trials. In this section the Testbed as a whole and its components individually are described. After the delineation of the system, a quick overview of the use case requirements (explicitly described in D2.1), the Valkyries architectural principles (described in D2.3) and the information flow for each use case (described in D2.3) will follow. The aim is to correlate and match the requirements and information flows with the modules of the Testbed and through this technical integration to execute and implement operational procedures in the use cases.

The Testbed offers a common ground for all use case systems, so they can communicate and understand each other. The main features of the Testbed are the Translation Plugins, provided by each Organisation.

5.2.1. Overview

Valkyries Testbed enables an examination workflow, which allows to receive a series of identified gaps in several domains such as methodological development paths, training methods enhancement and technological equipment upgrade, among others.

Such gaps are taken into account and confronted to simulated or emulated dataflows originating from several specialised external modules. In order to make a more efficient aggregation of data, thus producing relevant evidence, the Core Modules of the Testbed are the Audit Module and the Machine Communication Module.

Audit Module allows the Testbed to tag evidence related to one or more entries in the Gap Registry, facilitating a subsequent analysis on whether such gaps can be translated into opportunities which can be used in order to author an Improvement Plan.

The main function of the Machine Communication Module is to serve as a probe gathering raw evidence produced through a MiTM (man in the middle) intercept of all communication between the specialised external modules. In Valkyries Testbed, specialised external modules are partners' IT systems.

Figure 5 - Testbed Overall Architecture

Valkyries Interoperability Framework (VIF) components of Testbed

VIF establishes the rules and protocols enabling the sharing of services and applications. It complies with a set of principles, business processes, technologies and components that should be followed to become part of the Valkyries ecosystem.

The concept is presented in the next figure.

Figure 6 - Valkyries high-level framework concept (source deliverable D2.3)

The interaction between the different Services is achieved by either natively complying with the VIF design principles or can be realised by means of a “SIGRUN connector”.

The framework keeps services and applications independent from each other, thus facilitating integration in the Testbed.

As part of the Testbed environment and following the architecture in D2.3, a set of **core services** will be replicated in the Testbed meeting the VIF requirement. VIF core services replicated in the Testbed are:

- **Single-Sign-On (SSO) service:** it handles authentication in Valkyries across the different applications of the federation.
- **Registration service:** it enables registration of application or components, thus becoming known in Valkyries.
- **Message Broker service:** a centralised broker for Valkyries, following the publish-subscribe paradigm and supporting event notification for core and functional services.
- **NTP:** A service that sets the common time reference for all the data exchanged within the Valkyries.

- **Blockchain service (Security and metadata registration log):** A network service that records all the metadata of the messages exchanged and provides the security services to prevent data tempering to be unknown enabling privacy and data auditing.

In addition to the Valkyries core services, “data exchange services” and “operational services” can be configured and deployed in a modular way, to meet the needs of a demonstration.

VIF is further described in deliverable D2.3.

The key messaging processes to enable data exchange between different applications are:

1. The Data brokers

The data brokers connect the data between the different applications.

Figure 7 - Testbed Data Flow (Data Broker Producer/Consumer Communication Model)

Depending on the scenario case which shall generate data, different kind of external modules shall be plugged into the Testbed Machine Communication module. For such processes, it is expected each partner’s system, at least to provide a well-documented RESTful API. Nevertheless, due to rapid development cycles, it is extremely advisable that each exposed API interface is OpenAPI compliant, which facilitates coupling modules in a more agile way.

Figure 8 - OpenAPI Development Pattern

2. The Blockchain network

Regarding the security infrastructure of the overall architecture and the scenarios that will be used for the exercise-trials, it is expected to create APIs that can be accessed only by authorised users.

Using the blockchain technology, parties that will share information throughout the platform can be identified. Each party can be identified using a unique "key" (private wallet) to be recognised by the web services that will be developed in order to grant access to the system. Since blockchain is decentralised, it can be easily adapted and make the distribution of the keys into any type of web service easier. Each key will be created by the administrator and set to valid in order to provide further access points to the system. Once the key is set to valid each individual can be mapped and monitored every time it uses its key. There will be a unique timestamp into the blockchain, that marks the entrance and also which web services were used.

Blockchain storage is a method of storing data in a decentralised network that makes use of the free hard drive space of users all over the world. A decentralised infrastructure can address many issues present in a centralised system and is an alternative to centralised cloud storage. Distributed ledger technology is a prerequisite for blockchain (DLT). A decentralised database of data about transactions between different parties is what the DLT functions as. Operations are stored in the ledger as a series of blocks and are filled into the DLT in chronological order. A blockchain is made up of interconnected chains of blocks, each of which refers to the block before it.

Moreover, data can also be stored into the blockchain, thus making it more difficult to be altered or get access to them. Also, this can be made possible through using blockchain endpoints. Each endpoint will gain access to the blockchain, so data can be stored into decentralised databases. After that, access to these databases will be granted to valid keys that will be set with specific permissions to what type of data can be viewed. Data cannot be altered, even though, in case

of any change, the possibility of re-deployment of new smart contracts that will expand the existing structure exists.

Each process into the blockchain is recorded and can easily be accessible. Since processing of personal data will take place, a private blockchain is recommended, thus making the access to it more difficult and the data will be even more limited to other parties.

The blockchain endpoints resemble any other type of web service with the only difference that, instead of connecting it to a common database, it will go through the blockchain in order to store and validate data.

The Testbed can be performed with real or simulated data or with the combination of both. The output can be easily validated by third parties as to the content or transaction that occurred.

In blockchain storage, sharding is the process by which files are initially divided up. To avoid data loss in the event of a transmission error, each shard is duplicated. Additionally, a private key is used to encrypt the files, rendering it impossible for other network nodes to view them. The replicated shards are dispersed among global decentralised nodes. As a result of the interactions being documented in the blockchain ledger, the system is able to confirm and synchronise the transactions among the blockchain's nodes. These interactions will always be preserved by blockchain storage, and the data cannot be altered.

Blockchain storage is a potentially less expensive, more secure and more reliable alternative to centralised cloud storage.

Providers of centralised cloud storage prevent data loss by making copies of the data and storing it in different data centres. The large amount of data that is duplicated in this process can create excessive amounts of surplus information. Also, cloud storage requires enterprise-grade hardware for its data centres. These factors can make centralised data storage significantly more expensive than blockchain storage. Blockchain storage advocates assert that it can reduce the cost of centralised cloud storage by up to 90% by utilizing the free space on users' devices all over the world. Renting out the unused space on their hard drives to third parties can be profitable for both individuals and companies.

Data being spread across dozens of different nodes provides blockchain storage security benefits in addition to the ones already mentioned. It is more difficult for hackers to access the data when the files are encrypted and dispersed across the decentralised network. No central authority overseeing file access or holding the keys required to unlock the files exists. Since the user has complete control over the private keys, it is impossible for a third party to access the files. Sharding further increases privacy by preventing each node from being able to see the entire file's contents.

Blockchain storage may also enable quicker and more flexible storage systems because users can alter settings like redundancy and retrieval speed.

Blockchains are decentralised and distributed. Typically, a database is located in a single location, and only one administrator has access to it. The existence of a blockchain is not restricted to a single server or owner. It exists on numerous nodes, each of which belongs to a different user.

Blockchains cannot be changed (immutable). This implies that something can neither be deleted nor changed once it has been stored on the blockchain. It is a database that can only be

expanded upon; it cannot be changed or eliminated. The purpose of traditional transactional databases is to be updated. Right away, this means that some use cases—but not all—make blockchains ideal.

Blockchains do not have a single administrator, but many. As a result, there is no longer any need to believe in a single blockchain administrator or individual. The blockchain itself serves as a deterrent to fraud and other forms of mistrust.

For storing large file sizes, blockchains are not effective. Other than core ledger data and associated hashes, storing data "on-chain" can be very expensive and is not a very scalable or efficient method. Each time you want to read that data, there are fees that can add up per terabyte on the chain per transaction. Blockchains are almost entirely dependent on some kind of off-chain storage because most SLAs cannot afford to wait minutes per megabyte. When you require a record-keeping system with complete security, validity, and traceability, blockchain is a good fit. But underlying databases will continue to be essential for the storage of larger files and more associated metadata.

These two elements, the Data brokers and the Blockchain 2050, of SIGRUN combined provide the data registration, the logging of data flows and can be used to support the validation process.

Test environment simulation

In order to perform the tests and exercise-trials execution it is required to have actors (victims, first responders, vehicles, etc.) that feed the scenario execution with their data. These actors can be real actors or simulated, as presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9 - Testbed data source

The execution of the exercise-trials can use real data, simulated data or a combination of both, according to the definition of the trial scenario.

The simulated actor can either be a software agent, a pre-recorded emulation of data, or a digital twin component that simulates an actor behaviour.

Validation of the communication modules

To consider the validation and test of the communications modules, communication networks emulation will be used to simulate and test the impact of the networks performance (data rates, baud rates, latency, among others) in the system execution.

5.2.2. Gaps and Opportunities Registry

The Testbed shall contain a registry of, among others, methodological and technological gaps detected in cross-border First Aid Operations. Such registry entries come from the various Valkyries tasks outputs, WP3: Standardization and Certification Opportunities, WP4: Technological gaps, WP5: Methodological and Procedural Gaps, WP6: Gaps in Collaboration and Training.

Such Gaps must be accompanied with proposed tests and verifications, so that they can be confirmed and transformed into opportunities, in order to feed the opportunities registry.

A gap is transformed into an opportunity, when a series of tests is successfully passed, and it is confirmed, that when the suggested techniques and methodologies are implemented in the tests, improvements are introduced.

5.2.3. Machine Communications Module: Machine to Machine (M2M) Messaging

M2M Messaging Module is usually a Messaging Bus, which can adopt several network topologies and is able to operate, among other modes, in Unicast, Multicast, or Broadcast modes. A messaging bus may be a message queue such as MQTT.

Essential parts of the M2M Messaging system are the machine translation plugins, which enable coupling one organisation system to the SIGRUN common environment thus enabling their data sharing and processes chain, in such a manner that complete traceability can be attained inside the Audit Module.

The machine translation plugins shall be written by each technological provider who wants or is required to integrate his/her systems into the Testbed.

To avoid doubling efforts and increasing complexity, the Testbed M2M Messaging uses the same SIGRUN protocol as defined in the architecture deliverable D2.3.

5.2.4. Audit Module

The Audit module recollects and stores all types of information and transactions resulting from the process of the operation execution. It is based on a subscription model, as it receives logs from other modules.

The audit module has at least two essential functions: logging and reporting. The reporting module, through several plugins, must be able to translate all the raw logging data into gaps and opportunities registers, or at least able to update (modify) the existing ones.

Each test should be able to reconfigure the reporting module, so a distinct report output can be produced in order to confirm or not, the harmonisation of a technological or methodological opportunity.

A proposed Logging and Audit Suite is ELK (Elastic + Logstash + Kibana) which allows custom reports through code-based templates.

5.2.5. Relation of TESTBED to SIGRUN INTEGRATION

Figure 10 presents the overview of the test and validation framework. The Testbed uses the same infrastructure of the SIGRUN (Communications, data layers and protocol and the VIF services). The application used by the test cases uses PLUG-INS to enable them to also interface with the SIGRUN architecture. These applications are launched according to the trial-exercise scenario for each use case.

Figure 10 - Test and validation framework.

In order to generate the scenario, and in the absence of real cases scenarios, the trial-exercises exploit simulation elements that replicate the expected real behaviour, actions and roles as in real scenarios. These “actors Simulators” models simulate the interactions and behaviour of the actors within the context of the use case. Simulators can include the victims, ambulances, first responders, etc.

The Testbed provides the functions to match the gaps and the opportunities and record the audit data to assess the results.

5.2.6. Setup

In the following subchapters the setup of the Testbed is further elaborated.

5.2.6.1 Code Repository

Figure 11: Screenshot from INDRA's github, source: https://github.com/DigitalLabsIndra/VALKYRIES_TESTBED

5.2.6.2 Kubernetes Cluster Overview

Requirements for installing Valkyries Testbed are:

- A fully-fledged Kubernetes Cluster, with at least the following modules
 - CNI Plugin
 - LoadBalancer
 - Persistent Volume Objects
- An internet connection (in order to download source code and necessary pods)
- Helm client installed on client machine

Install steps are the following (to be executed from a command line through git and kubectl):

```
git clone https://github.com/DigitalLabsIndra/VALKYRIES\_TESTBED.git
cd VALKYRIES_TESTBED
kubectl apply -f environment/
kubectl config set-context --current --namespace=valkyries-dev
helm repo add elastic https://helm.elastic.co
helm repo update
cd components/ELK
```

```
helm install elk-elasticsearch elastic/elasticsearch -f instalar_e.yaml --namespace valkyries-dev
helm install elk-kibana elastic/kibana -f instalar_k.yaml --namespace valkyries-dev
helm install elk-logstash elastic/logstash -f instalar_l.yaml --namespace valkyries-dev
helm install elk-filebeat elastic/filebeat -f instalar_b.yaml --namespace valkyries-dev
cd ../..
kubectl apply -f components/mosquitto/
```

5.2.6.3 Connect to Azure VPN

Requirements:

- ((Azure VPN Windows client)) ([link](#))
- MacOS/GNU-Linux OpenVPN client (command line)
- A certificate file provided by the Testbed Administrator
- If using Windows, have IPsec and IKE service enabled.

Azure VPN config files can be downloaded from the Azure Web interface. Nevertheless, an administrator can download them, for better convenience of the end-user.

Figure 12: Azure VPN config files Download page

Figure 13: Azure VPN config files Download page

5.2.6.3.1 Windows

Install the above-mentioned .pfx certificate in personal storage.

Unzip the zip file and get the .xml configuration file and proceed to import into Azure VPN Client.

Nombre	Fecha de modifica
AzureVPN	22/06/2022 10:55
Generic	22/06/2022 10:55
OpenVPN	22/06/2022 10:55
WindowsAmd64	22/06/2022 10:55
WindowsX86	22/06/2022 10:55

Figure 14: Azure VPN XML Config file

Figure 15: Azure VPN XML Config file

Once .xml config file is loaded, it should be parsed and become usable

Figure 16: Azure VPN XML Config file

Figure 17: Azure VPN XML Config file

Figure 18: Connect to Azure VPN on Windows

Figure 19: Disconnect from Azure VPN on Windows

5.2.6.3.2 MacOS/GNU-Linux

Place all files in the same folder (.crt, .key, .ovpn).

```
burrito:~/valk_vpn >>> ls  
kub.crt kub.key vpnconfig.ovpn
```

Figure 20: Azure VPN OpenVPN files

Execute openvpn with mentioned files

```
sudo openvpn vpnconfig.ovpn
```

Provide certificate private password (do not share such password).

```
burrito:~/valk_vpn >>> sudo openvpn vpnconfig.ovpn  
Enter Private Key Password: *****)
```

Figure 21: If working, OpenVPN should stay open

5.2.6.4 Daily Operation

Depending on the Kubernetes Cluster, mileage may vary. In this demo, an AKS has been used (Amazon Kubernetes Cluster). AKS Load Balancer and Azure VPN provide External IPs and also identity and security of the access.

The requirements for operating the Valkyries Testbed are:

- A computer with internet connection
- A VPN Client and a personal cryptographic certificate (intended to be used with Azure VPN)
- An Azure VPN client file (intended to use through an OpenVPN or Azure Client VPN Client)

AKS Services external IPs can be obtained by consulting admin web panel, be it Kubernetes Dashboard or Azure AKS Dashboard

Name	Namespace	Status	Type	Cluster IP	External IP	Ports
kubernetes	default	Ok	ClusterIP	10.0.0.1		443/T
kube-dns	kube-system	Ok	ClusterIP	10.0.0.10		53/UI
metrics-server	kube-system	Ok	ClusterIP	10.0.228.83		443/T
kubernetes-internal	default	Ok	LoadBalancer	10.0.101.43	192.168.100.128	80:31
elasticsearch-master	valkyries-dev	Ok	ClusterIP	10.0.148.29		9200/
elasticsearch-master-h...	valkyries-dev	Ok	ClusterIP	None		9200/
elk-kibana-kibana	valkyries-dev	Ok	ClusterIP	10.0.56.123		5601/
elk-logstash-logstash	valkyries-dev	Ok	ClusterIP	10.0.7.100		5044/
elk-logstash-logstash-h...	valkyries-dev	Ok	ClusterIP	None		9600/
mosquito	valkyries-dev	Ok	ClusterIP	10.0.9.231		1883/

Figure 22: VALKYRIES Testbed Kubernetes Services Overview

Refresh

Namespace: valkyries-dev

Labels: -

Selector: app=mosquito

Creation time: 2022-07-21T16:22:16.000Z

Type: ClusterIP

Cluster IP: 10.0.9.231

External IP: -

Session affinity: None

See more

Name	Node port	Port	Protocol	Target port	Endpoints
-	-	1883	TCP	1883	192.168.100.72:1883

Figure 23: VALKYRIES Testbed Kubernetes MQTT Overview

Figure 24: VALKYRIES Testbed Kubernetes Kibana Overview

Once connected to the VPN, Audit Module (ELK) and M2M Machine communication module can be accessed.

```
~/valk_vpn >>> sudo openvpn vpnconfig.ovpn
[sudo] password for luser:
Enter Private Key Password: *****
```

Figure 25: Azure VPN Connection

```
mosquitto_sub
openvpn  mosquitto_sub  ~/valk_vpn
Type 'help' to know the ton of Elive features available...
~/valk_vpn >>> mosquitto_sub -h 192.168.100.72 -t A_topic
Hello World
```

Figure 26: Subscribing to a topic, in MQTT

```
~/valk_vpn
openvpn  mosquitto_sub  ~/valk_vpn
Type 'help' to know the ton of Elive features available...
~/valk_vpn >>> mosquitto_pub -h 192.168.100.72 -t A_topic -m "Hello World"
~/valk_vpn >>> []
```

Figure 27: Publishing a Short message tagged with a topic

Whilst MQTT is command line based, ELK applicative is to be accessed through a browser:

192.168.100.118:5601/app/home#/

Figure 28: ELK Web Interface

5.2.7 First version of the demonstration of the Testbed

Deliverable 7.1, apart from a report, is also a demonstrator. To this direction a video has been developed to briefly depict the setup of the Testbed. In the following link, access to the demo video is provided.

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1z7lju8HetmH5Lgze1pOaP57ZhTvPwuGU/view?usp=sharing>

6 Testing strategy

This chapter is dedicated to the outline of exercises for first responders. The types and phases of exercises, as well as the different types of participants along with their roles and responsibilities are described. Moreover, the four use cases and their requirements are presented, building upon previous deliverables, but also providing some new information about the interactions between the participants.

6.1 Deployment of use cases in Exercise-Trials

According to ISO 22398 “an exercise is a process to train for, assess, practice and improve performance in an organization”. Hence, by definition, in an exercise the performance of an organisation against a system/tool, a protocol, a plan, an operational procedure, personnel capability, among others, is examined. The scope of an exercise is to enhance the capabilities of organisations and the training of the personnel to new technologies and processes, as well as the facilitation of inter-organisational and cross-border cooperation.

There are two main types of exercises, the **discussion-based** exercises and the **operations-based** exercises. According to the United States Department for Homeland Security (2020), *discussion-based exercises* are used for the familiarisation of organisations and their personnel with existing plans, agreements and policies. In this type of exercise, tabletop exercises, workshops and seminars are included. *Operations-based exercises* implement, test and validate exercises plans, policies, agreements etc. in an operational environment with resources mobilisation and real time reaction. Drills and full-scale exercises are encompassed in this type of exercises. The individual, as well as organisational performance can be assessed, and gaps can be identified.

Taking into account that in the Valkyries use cases an ensemble of tools and procedures is going to be tested, the demonstrators will be conducted in a specific type of exercise, where the scope is not the training and evaluation of the players performance, but rather the testing of a new solution e.g., a technological tool, doctrine, standard, process, concept, methodology or any combination thereof, is performed. Therefore, the demonstrators of Valkyries aiming at the testing of harmonisation opportunities as new solutions, are considered “**trials**”, following the definition of CWA 17514. According to CWA 17514, “a trial is an event for systematically assessing solutions for current and emerging needs in such a way that practitioners can do this following a pragmatic and systematic approach”. In other words, **during a trial, solutions are validated by practitioners in the context of realistic situations and operational environment**. Trials may be deployed in the form of discussion-based or small-scale operations-based exercises.

6.2 Participants and Roles in an Exercise-Trial

The participants of an exercise-trial can be clustered in four main categories. Their involvement and their role in evaluation is distinct:

1. The **players**, who are practically the ones with active roles in exercises. These are most often practitioners who will eventually be the end-users of the solutions. The players are the participants with hands-on experience in the exercise-trial and evaluation from the end-user perspective is mainly expected by them. Their feedback is expected via a participant feedback form.
2. The **observers**, who spectate the exercise without being actively involved in the exercise and register information for their own purposes. Observers may be additional representatives of organisations that participate as players and/or external

stakeholders. They may be also part of the evaluation process if requested by the exercise manager and/or evaluation lead.

3. The **evaluator(s)**, individuals(s) with significant expertise, are responsible for the collection of all data related to the exercise, the assessment of these data and the compilation of final evaluation conclusions. For the case of exercise-trials, in which solutions are tested with the active involvement of players, the role of the evaluators focuses on the provision of feedback on the observed performance of solutions, the way the players interacted with them and the added value they estimate the tested solution will bring to crisis management.
4. **Solution providers** are technical or research providers of tools or methodologies who have the main responsibility of guaranteeing the smooth operation of tools and/or to confirm the relevance of the methodology/process with the scenario deployed.

Roles of the exercise managing team

According to scientific literature e.g., the “Trial Guidance Methodology Handbook”, developed under the framework of the FP7 Driver + project, and also based on the authors’ expertise in the organisation of exercises and trials, the roles and responsibilities of the exercise management team are presented:

- **Exercise manager** is the one responsible for the overall organisation of the exercise. His/her responsibilities include the final decisions regarding the scenario of the exercise, the evaluation methodology that will be followed after the completion of the exercise, the technological solution that will be examined throughout the exercise, the resources to be used and the end users, who will participate in the exercise, in common coordination with the scenario planner, the evaluation leader, the technical coordinator, the logistics coordinator and the end users coordinator respectively. The exercise manager is also responsible for risk management and for defining the appropriate mitigation measures in cooperation with the rest of the exercise planning team. On the occasion that the exercise is of a large scale and has complexities a whole team could be engaged in the management of the exercise.
- **Technical coordinator** is the one responsible for the operation of technological solutions that will be tested individually or integrated in a platform during the exercise. Moreover, adequate training of the users prior to the exercise conduct is included in his/her responsibilities, as well as the metrics and performance indicators, which will be used for the technical verification of the solutions in collaboration with the technological providers.
- **Scenario planner** is responsible for the building and implementation of the scenario, based on which the exercise will be executed. He/she has to take into consideration the scope and objectives of the exercise and also the identified gaps, which are meant to be covered by the solutions examined in the context of the exercise. The scenario has to be as realistic as possible, needs to serve the scope of the exercise and the functionalities of the solutions so that it allows their objective assessment. Moreover, the scenario planner has to develop the scenario in such a way, that the identified gaps and problems will be addressed in the exercise.
- **Evaluation leader** is the leader of the evaluation team the responsibilities of which are the development of the overall evaluation methodology that is going to be followed during the whole exercise cycle, from the preparation to the review phase. Especially, in the case of an exercise-trial (as is the case in the Valkyries project) the evaluation

methodology consists of two pillars, the methodology and definition of performance indicators which will be developed for the validation of the under-examination solutions by the end users and the methodology and KPIs for the technical verification of the solutions. For the latter, the technological providers' and apparently the technical coordinator's involvement is foreseen.

- **Logistic coordinator/Host** is responsible for the location, at which the exercise will be held and for the essential resources i.e., equipment and materials, apart from the technological solutions, that will be used to support the overall execution of the exercise.
- **End-users' coordinator** is responsible to assist the exercise manager or exercise management team with regards to the definition of the relevant end users, who will participate in the exercise and to make the appropriate contacts and provide information to them.
- **Exercise safety officer** is the person responsible for the safety of all participants while performing the activities during the exercise. This person should be involved from the planning phase of the exercise until the review, in which lessons learned related to exercise safety need to be documented. In case safety is compromised, the exercise safety officer needs to intervene immediately.

6.3 The phases of an Exercise-Trial

According to ISO 22398, an exercise can be divided in three basic phases:

1. The planning phase of the exercise
2. The exercise conduct
3. Review and improvement of the exercise

Figure 29 - Exercise-trial cycle

A trial is structured and developed following the exercises development approach taking into account that the main scope is shifted from the training and assessment of the participants' performance to the testing and evaluation of solutions by them.

Planning Phase

The planning phase is the first step in the organisation of an exercise. At this stage, it is crucial to identify the gaps that first responders face in their daily operations and the solutions that are developed and tested in the trials. This is composed by the following steps:

1. The organisation has to perform a needs analysis in order to identify the gaps and core objectives of the exercise
2. To select the solutions that will be tested
3. To analyse the expectations of the participating organisations with regards to the tested solutions,
4. To define the roles and responsibilities of each participant and set priorities,
5. To formulate the scenario, based on which the solutions will be examined,
6. To design the data collection plan and
7. To set the basis and the criteria for the evaluation of the solutions, which is twofold:
 - a. Technical verification of the solutions by the technological providers
 - b. Validation of the solutions by the end users, who, in the case of the Valkyries project, are the first responders.

It is highlighted that the players, with their roles and organisations, need to be identified and confirmed, as the scenario, to be developed, needs to be compatible to their capabilities and roles and it has to engage to some extent all of them.

The design is managed by the appointed exercise manager and is a collective and participatory phase in which solution providers and end-users identify their needs and expectations. Below, the necessary roles for an exercise-trial development are proposed. At first, the scope and the objectives of the exercise are set, as well as the solutions which will be tested. The objectives are directly correlated to the evaluation criteria aiming to the validation of the solution, the familiarisation of the end-users with it and the collection of the expected feedback. Considering the outline of the use case, the scenario, based on which the exercise will be conducted, is developed aiming at the creation of the operational context. Following the definition of the scenario, it may be further refined with the identification of potential injects that will guide the flow of the scenario and the exercise deployment. This way, the framework under which the solutions will be tested, will be defined, allowing for the development of the plan for the documentation and collection of all data, related to the performance of the under-examination solutions, and for the definition of the roles and responsibilities of the participants. Moreover, it is within this phase that the evaluation methodology, the criteria and metrics that will be used for the verification and validation of the solutions are identified.

During the planning phase, the following actions need to be taken as far as the Testbed is concerned:

1. A template of the Testbed operational scenario is selected, adapted to and loaded into the Testbed (it is loaded in a machine and human readable format and in any case in a structured information format). It includes risks, tasks, impact registry, countermeasures, risk mitigation controls as a minimum.
2. A risk analysis prior to the operation is carried out. A risk analysis includes review of preloaded risk-related registries, and the creation of new ones, if necessary, i.e., impact assessment, possible impact propagation, countermeasures catalogue, risk mitigation controls.
3. A list of possible injectable hazard and threats is reviewed.

4. A task review prior to the operation is done. A task review goes through review of the task planning, the task dependencies, periodic tasks and injectable tasks.
5. Pre-operation organisation identities are initialised.
6. Federation contracts are established among organisations.
7. Resources brought by organisations are reviewed and validated.

Exercise Conduct

At this stage the exercise programme is implemented following the lay out of the planning phase. The conduct and the final preparations will differ depending on the type of the exercise. Moreover, depending on the size of the exercise one or more preparatory meetings may be required, either with all exercise participants or per thematic groups or roles.

Final preparations consist of:

- Preliminary tests to be conducted beforehand in order to ensure that all functionalities of the system are working in a proper manner and interoperability between the modules of the platform is achieved. The operational capacity of the overall system is thus tested and ensured.
- All supporting means for scenario deployment (e.g., printouts, videos, locations in maps) are finalised and put in place.
- All documents and means (e.g., video recordings etc.) for data collection are prepared and put in place.
- Confirmation of participant's presence, appointment of roles (players, evaluators, observers) and position allocation.

The exercise initiates with the introduction of all participants and presentation of the exercise manager of the scope of the exercise, the scenario context and the expected results. General instructions are given about logistics, the agenda, the role assignment (if simulated) to participants and their expected actions. The solutions, if they haven't been presented at a previous meeting, need to be discussed. In case of technical tools to be tested within the exercise, the participants need to be familiarised with them with hands-on experience, ideally at an earlier meeting. The involvement of the solutions into the scenario is explained.

The evaluation leader provides the appointed evaluators with the Evaluation guide. This is a document that contains the exercise performance objectives, capability targets that are being tested and respective critical tasks with evaluation requirements, aiming to the guidance of evaluators for data collection. The latter, in particular for the case of an exercise-trial, needs to be aligned with the exercise objectives, validation and evaluation needs for the solutions tested, the roles of the players and critical activities that are requested to perform in relation to the solutions, compatible to their professional position and/or simulated role. This activity may be also performed during a preparatory meeting organised by the evaluation leader with participation of other members of the exercise managing team.

The exercise manager announces the beginning of the exercise and the development of the scenario begins. Geographical and time-related issues are given, as well as the threats, hazards and incidents that occur following the scenario. The players are expected to interact with the solutions and among each other, according to their operational or simulated role.

During the exercise conduct, data are collected by evaluators, observers and other potential means that have been put in place (e.g., video recordings, GPS tracking, tools log files, etc.)

The conduct phase is concluded with the wrap-up activities and debriefings. At this stage, additional data used for the evaluation are collected. During the wrap-up stage a hot wash debriefing meeting, focus groups and one-by-one interviews could be held, in which on the spot discussions regarding first impressions, identified strengths and weaknesses of the examined solution and suggestions for improvements are made. These can be moderated by the **evaluation leader** or the **exercise manager**. The post-exercise debrief is essential part of the exercise and although it shall be of short duration, sufficient time should be allocated.

During the exercise conduct, all actions taken by the players need to employ the solutions, where applicable, and thus the different modules of the Testbed are activated.

Review and Improvement

This is the final phase of an exercise, in which the evaluation data is compiled and analysed and results are documented. The evaluators collect all data and observations concentrated throughout the implementation of the exercise, as well as conclusions, remarks and comments from the players' hot wash debrief. Moreover, the players will document their feedback through the *participant feedback form (USDHS, 2020)* which will be populated during this phase. The evaluation methodology is designed during the planning phase of the exercise. The way data is collected, analysed and assessed is also outlined at the initial stages. The evaluation team might be comprised of an evaluation leader who has the experience and competence to oversee the whole exercise and is responsible for its evaluation overall. Evaluation differs, depending on the type of the exercise, and its span covers everything, from a simple documentation of the discussions and exchange of opinions between the players, in a discussion-based exercise, to the validation of the players' capabilities in implementing standard operational procedures, plans and protocols, in an operations-based exercise.

In particular for an exercise-trial, as is the case in the Valkyries project among others, the evaluation focuses almost exclusively to the solution and its functionalities. The evaluation team together with the exercise managing team documents the most important outcomes of the exercise-trial focusing on the validation of the solutions by end-users, their contribution to crisis management, their adoption willingness by participant organisations and other solution-related topics. Moreover, the evaluation of the exercise conduct itself can be performed, analysing feedback collected by participants which aim is the improvement of the testing process and other organisational aspects.

According to the CWA 17514 a trial can be assessed under the scope of three different but interconnected dimensions:

1. The first dimension is related to the solution itself, its assessment by the end users and the added value that it brings to stakeholders.
2. The second dimension is related to crisis management, the impact it has on the trial and the way with which the tested solution influences the operations of a first responders' organisation.
3. The third dimension is related to the trial organisation itself, how it affects the organisation of the exercise and what changes it introduces to the exercise.

In operational exercises, performance and capabilities associated to exercise objectives, as well as evaluation outcomes, are documented in the After-Action report. In case of exercise-trials, all data and conclusions are included in relevant deliverables, as well as documents for internal and external dissemination. The contents of these reports include the most important observations from the exercise, conclusions drawn from the operation of the solutions, the evaluation and lessons learned accompanied with recommendations for improvement of the examined solution.

Following the evaluation of the exercise an improvement plan is developed. This plan, as its name suggests, focuses on the analysis of the weaknesses of the solutions, functionalities that do not meet the user requirements, as well as strong points of the solutions that could be further enhanced or around which the rest of the tools/systems/methods may be developed. A map of corrective actions may be then provided, which need to be implemented aiming at the continual improvement of the system both as a whole and of its components individually.

During the review phase, the following actions as far as the Testbed is concerned need to be taken:

1. All audit registries are saved for post operation analysis.
2. A post-operation risk analysis is done. A risk analysis includes review of all risk-related registries, impact and loss assessment, review efficacy of countermeasures and risk mitigation controls.
3. Injected hazards and threats are reviewed, and possibly integrated in standard mission risk catalogue.
4. A post-operation task review is done. A task review goes through review of task planning, task dependencies, periodic tasks and injectable tasks. KPIs are reviewed regarding tasks final status and metrics.
5. Federation contracts are cancelled.
6. Resources brought by organizations are reviewed and off boarded.

6.4 Testbed and use cases

At the current phase of the project, the specific technological tools to be used and tested per use case have not been clearly selected and thus, the specificities of each Testbed (hardware and software) cannot be described other than the architecture and main modules described in Section 5.2. On the other hand, it is essential to include a brief overview of the use cases and a description of the interactions that will take place and the functionalities to be employed, based on which the final Testbed design will take place. Finalisation of the use case scenarios and the actual tools, systems, applications that will be integrated and implemented throughout the trials will be defined in the second versions of Deliverables 2.1 and 2.3. Nevertheless, it is confirmed that the modules currently anticipated for the Testbed will serve the technological and operational requirements of the tools and procedures to be harmonized in each use case and jointly tested during each exercise-trial.

6.5 Use cases and key requirements

The following subchapters (6.5.1 to 6.5.4) provide a brief overview of the four use cases as well as the information flows and interactions between the different participants, that will participate.

6.5.1 Use case 1 Spain-Portugal

Use case 1 refers to a Cross-Border emergency intervention that represent a forest wildfire involving Spain and Portugal. A series of fire outbreaks is observed in a secluded area of significant ecological value in the proximity of the Spanish and Portuguese borders. Weather conditions are conducive for a rapid fire spread, with strong winds, low humidity and high temperatures prevailing for a long period of time. Moreover, the mountainous topography and the dense forests of the area complicate the arrival of first responders’ resources. Due to the quick spread of the fire victims have been reported, that require triage and immediate transfer to nearby hospitals, whereas there is also information about people trapped in cars and potential deaths. A large number of ambulances is required for the provision of first aid to the victims, as well as effective collaboration between the different types of first responders arriving at the scene.

In the following table, deriving from D.2.3, the actors, who are going to participate in the use case are presented along with the technological tools that will be used.

Operational Actors	Technological Artefacts
Citizens	User Terminal (e.g., Mobile phone), Web-client
Firefighters / First Responders	Wearables (e.g., activity tracker with GNSS) User Terminal (e.g., Professional Mobile Phone with AWARE App) Tetra Terminal
Advanced Medical Post	User Terminal
PSAP Operator (Public Safety Answering Point) - Coordination Centre 112 Extremadura	User Terminal: 112 Terminal and emergency call management system
PSAP Operator (Public Safety Answering Point) - Coordination Centre 112 Portugal	User Terminal: 112 Terminal and emergency call management system
Command Post	APP iSafety
Hospital	Web Portal (Monitor), APP_AWARE
Political Liaison	User Terminal (e.g., Phone / E-mail)
First Aid Vehicles / AMBULANCE	- Vehicle Terminal - Wi-Fi network, cellular connection (4G/5G) - GNSS_device APP AWARE
Victims	User Terminal (e.g., Mobile Phone) wearables

Table 1 - UC1 Actors and Technological Artefacts Mapping (Source: D2.3)

The following Information flows were derived for UC1:

INFO FLOW	DESCRIPTION
1. Alert	Communication of a medical emergency by a citizen via an emergency call
2. Raises Alert	Reports the emergency case to the command centre
3. Dispatch	Forwards the emergency case to the Advanced Command post, in response to a confirmed incident
4. Situational Awareness	Report Incident victims and medical status and data received, including victims, FR and assets location status and priority.
5. Register victim	Victim ID; triage data
6. Report first response data	FR position, ID, status

INFO FLOW	DESCRIPTION
7. Victim data	Victim data update: symptoms, medical information; status (triage). Emergency case file updated.
8. Dispatch AMBULANCE	Dispatch information: task victim to an ambulance ID, victim registration ID
9. Dispatch Victim to Hospital	Ambulance task ID, service ID, Destination, Victim registration ID, Emergency case file updated; victim pathology
10. Report ambulance data	Ambulance position, ETA, victims ID, victims incident origin
11. Report victim data	Victim ID; victim health data (ambulance or wearable devices); Victim triage colour change
12. Report response availability	Hospital capability and availability to handle victim's, number, and type of medical emergency
13. Reference Alert	Cross—Border incident data alert
14. Incident Report (SP)	Data on cross-border confirmed incidents (SP)
15. Incident Report (PT)	Data on cross-border confirmed incidents (PT)
16. Political Coordination	Countries authorization and political agreements
17. OPS Report	Operational key status: results; situational awareness of high risks elements;

Table 2 - UC1 information flow (Source D2.3)

The following interaction scheme represents the actions and capabilities that will be implemented in use case 1.

Figure 12 - UC1 Interaction Diagram (source D2.3)

The abovementioned information flow will be conducted by the following actors, as identified by Deliverable 2.3 for the UC1 and will be supported by the following technological tools:

6.5.2 Use case 2 Slovakia-Italy

Use case 2 refers to a cross-border emergency intervention in case of a Toxic Leakage incident involving Slovakia and Italy (due to the fact that there is no partner from Austria in the consortium, Italy is considered a neighbour of Slovakia). The toxic cloud coming from the fire is threatening densely populated territory of Slovakia, as well as its border area (IT). The plume containing isocyanates is spreading by the wind. Within a range of 10-15 km the levels of toxicity are expected to be very high/seriously dangerous. A large number of victims are reported to the hotline. Several units from different first responders’ organisations arrive at the scene and therefore effective cooperation among them is required. Effective communication and harmonized procedures are needed, especially in view of the cross-border threat.

The following table from D2.3 presents the actors of the UC and the tools to be used.

Operational Actors	Technological Artefacts
Citizens	User Terminal (e.g., Mobile phone), Web-client
Integrated Rescue System (IRS)	APP_ISAFETY
Fire and Rescue Service (FRS)	GNSS_Tracker Mobile Phone
Emergency Medical Service (EMS) - First Aid Vehicles / AMBULANCE	GNSS_Tracker Mobile Phone WebApp EmMa (IT) <u>Vehicle terminal:</u> - Newtork Wi-Fi / xG connection - GNSS - APP_MONITOR
	- APP InPrimis (IT)
Police	GNSS_Tracker Mobile Phone
FRS – HAZMAT team	User Terminal
Police – CBRN Unit	User Terminal
EMS – CBRN Unit (IT)	User Terminal / Phone
Commander (SK)	Phone / Email / CISE
Commander (IT)	Phone / Email / CISE
Political Liaison (IT/SK)	Phone / E-mail
EUCPM	Phone / Email / Tech services [CISE / Copernicus services / ERCC services]
Hospital	APP_AWARE
Victims	User Terminal wearables
Civil protection	User Terminal (e.g., Mobile / dedicated Coms)
Control chemical laboratory	User Terminal (e.g., Mobile phone)
Military forces	User Terminal (e.g., Mobile / dedicated Coms)

Table 3 - UC2 Actors and Technological Artefacts Mapping (Source D2.3)

The aforementioned actors are expected to communicate with each other in the way the following information flow suggests.

INFO FLOW	DESCRIPTION
1. Alert	Communication of the incident detection from any source.
2. Raises Alert	Reports credible incident alerts received to the proper command centre
3. Command	Information on C2 Course of Action

4. Operational coordination	Cross—Border incident data information, data shared and coordination between the response assets.
5. Coordination CBRN	Report Incident to CBRN police, incident data
6. Victim data	Victim ID data, symptoms, Victim medical data; wearables health data, privacy authorization
7. Dispatch Victim to Hospital	Ambulance task ID, service ID, Destination, Victim registration ID
8. Report victim data	Victim ID; victim health data, position, ETA
9. Incident Report (SP)	Data on cross-border confirmed incidents (SK)
10. Incident Report (PT)	Data on cross-border confirmed incidents (IT)
11. Political Coordination	Countries authorization and political agreements, Support Request to EU
12. Situational Awareness	Report Incident victims and field Combat status, including victims, their location and priority.

Table 4 - UC2 Information Flows (Source D2.3)

The following interaction scheme represents the actions and capabilities that will be implemented in use case 2.

Figure 31 - UC2: Interaction Diagram on the side of Italian Republic

6.5.3 Use case 3 Bulgaria-Greece

Use case 3 refers to a cross-border emergency intervention in case of an Earthquake incident involving Bulgaria and Greece. The earthquake has a magnitude of 6.5 on the Richter scale resulting in a large number of victims. Moreover, there is leakage of acrylonitrile as a result of a reservoir failure at a polymer plant near the town of Petrich. In addition to the consequences of the earthquake, large amounts of precipitation due to rainfalls lasting for several days have resulted in partial floods, whereas there is unconfirmed information that there are cracks in the Logodazh dam, which is in the proximity of the worst affected by the earthquake areas. Communications are seriously disrupted and heavy traffic is observed as a result of thousands of citizens abandoning the areas. Several first responder units are deployed to the affected area for the identification of victims and health assistance to the casualties. Collaboration and coordination among different teams are needed.

In the following table the actors that are going to participate in the Use case are presented, along with the technological equipment that is foreseen to be used. This table is derived from D2.3 “Overarching Architecture”.

Operational Actors	Technological Artefacts
National Centre of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography, Bulgarian Academy of Science (Simulated role)	Mobile phones, terrestrial phones, PCs and connection to the Internet.
Coordination Centre 112 Bulgaria (Simulated role)	112 Terminal and emergency call management system, PCs and connection to the Internet, emergency management software.

Operational Actors	Technological Artefacts
Bulgarian Red Cross (Real actors)	Radio-stations and mobile phones
Bulgarian Fire Brigade (Real actors)	Radio-stations, TETRA mobile phones, and mobile phones
Military medical academy team (Real actors)	Radio-stations, TETRA mobile phones, and mobile phones
Bulgarian Emergency ambulance service	Radio-stations and mobile phones
Bulgarian military unit (CBRN) (Real actors)	Radio-stations and mobile phones. Mobile command-staff vehicle with PCs and connection to the Internet.
Political Liaison (Simulated role)	Radio-stations and mobile phones
Civil Protection authorities (Real actors)	Radio-stations and mobile phones
Coordination Centre 112 Greece (Simulated role)	112 Terminal and emergency call management system, PCs and connection to the internet, emergency management software.
Hellenic Rescue Team (Real actors)	Radio-stations and mobile phones
Hellenic Fire Brigade (Observers)	Radio-stations and mobile phones
Hellenic National Centre for Emergency Assistance (Simulated role)	Mobile phones, terrestrial phones, PCs and connection to the Internet.
Hellenic Earthquake Planning and Protection Organization (EPPO) (Simulated role)	Mobile phones, terrestrial phones, PCs and connection to the Internet.
Citizens (Real actors)	Mobile phones, terrestrial phones, social media
Victims (Real actors)	User Terminal (Mobile phones)
Hospital (Real hospital)	Mobile phones, terrestrial phones, APP_MONITOR
Ambulance (Real ambulance)	APP_AWARE

Table 5 - UC3 Actors and Technological Artefacts Mapping (Source D2.3)

Additionally, because the communications in the area are disrupted (according to the use case), it is foreseen to be used a prototype of a mobile base station, based on software-defined radio. Besides, using a UAV for monitoring the affected area is envisaged. These two prototypes of tools will be provided by BDI.

The table below depicts the information flow between the aforementioned actors for the third use case.

INFO FLOW	DESCRIPTION
1. BG ALERT	Communication of the incident detection from the National Centre of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography of the Bulgarian Academy of Science.
2. BG COMMAND POST - BG Raises alert	Reports credible incident alerts received to the proper command centre.
3. BG Dispatch	Data required to deploy a local Command post, in response to a confirmed incident
4. Situational awareness	Report Incident victims and medical situation, data received

INFO FLOW	DESCRIPTION
5. BG Incident reported	Data on cross-border confirmed incidents (BG)
6. BG Public order and humanitarian assistance	Citizen ID data, status, agency in charge, instructions, destination
7. BG Public warning	Agency in charge, instructions, means
8. BG Victim data	Victim ID data, health data, privacy authorization
9. BG First responder data	FR position, ID, status
10. BG-GR Reference alert	Data on cross-border confirmed incidents
11. GR Incident reported	Data on cross-border confirmed incidents
12. BG-GR Political coordination	Countries authorization and political agreements
13. GR COMMAND POST - GR Raises alert	Reports credible incident alerts received to the proper command centre.
14. GR Public warning	Agency in charge, instructions, means
15. GR Dispatch	Data required to deploy a local Command post, in response to a confirmed incident
16. Situational awareness	Report Incident victims and medical situation, data received
17. GR Public order and humanitarian assistance	Citizen ID data, status, agency in charge, instructions, destination
18. GR Victim data	Victim ID data, health data, privacy authorization
19. GR First responder data	FR position, ID, status
20. BG-GR Dispatch victim to Hospital	Ambulance ID, service ID, Destination, Victim registration ID
21. BG-GR Report victim data	Ambulance position, ETA, victims ID, victims incident origin
22. BG-GR Ambulance data	Victim ID; victim health data

Table 6 - UC3 information flow (Source D2.3)

The following interaction scheme represents the actions and capabilities that will be implemented in use case 3.

Figure 32 - UC3: interaction Diagram (Source D2.3)

6.5.4 Use case 4 Norway-Denmark-The Netherlands

Use case 4 refers to a cross-border emergency intervention in case of a Maritime Search and Rescue incident involving Norway, Denmark and Sweden. The scenario evolves around the collision of a passenger ship with a tanker carrying dangerous chemicals in the waters between Denmark and Norway. The collision results in injuries and the outbreak of fire, which smoke is assumed poisonous. Moreover, an unknown number of people has to be rescued from the sea before they freeze to death, whereas it is also crucial to maintain the fire before it gets out of control. The number of firefighters on board is limited and the means and special equipment for the suppression of the fire are missing. There is serious threat that if the fire is not contained in time, it will cause serious environmental damage. Assistance from the air and sea is imperative for both the SAR and the oil/chemical spill cleaning procedures.

The abovementioned information flow will be conducted by the following actors, as identified by Deliverable 2.3 for the UC4 and will be supported by the following technological tools:

Operational Actors	Technological Artefacts
Pollution Combat Vessel	GMDSS, Phone, Email, APP_KystInfo
On-Scene commander	GMDSS, Phone, Email, APP_KystInfo
Coastal administration (NO)	Phone / Email, APP_KystInfo
Maritime administration (SE)	Phone / Email
Political Liaison (NO/SE)	Phone / E-mail
Vicinity Vessel support SAR	GMDSS

Operational Actors	Technological Artefacts
Victims	User Terminal (e.g., Mobile phone), distress beacon <> or nothing
Vessel in distress	AIS / EPIRB / distress beacon => via GMNDSS
RCC (HRS)	GMDSS, Phone, Email, APP_KystInfo
RPAS / AOC	APP_RPAS_Mission

Table 7 - UC4 Actors and Technological Artefacts Mapping (Source D2.3)

The following table depicts the information flow that has been identified to take place between the aforementioned actors:

INFO FLOW	DESCRIPTION
1. MAYDAY Alert	Communication of the incident detection from any source. Include name, call sign and position of vessel
2. Radio Coms	First-on Scene Ship informs RCC if it is able to assist
3. Engage Rescue	First-on Scene Ship starts rescue Victim ID data, symptoms, Victim medical data; wearables health data, privacy authorization
4. Radio Coms	First-on Scene ship keeps RCC informed
5. Notify and engage OSC	Assign On-Scene Commander (OSC) to the Coast Guard Vessel. Report on the Vessel (assets) capacity to comply with the course of action Report execution status
6. Engage Rescue	The more capable resource will be engaged by the OSC.
7. Engage Fire Fighters	Deploy fire-fighters
8. Engage Air Support	Mission flight request + POI + sensor selection
9. Situation update	Keep the RCC updated when new information is available.
10. Air Mission Data	- Telemetry: Drone flight status + drone path - Mission data: sensors data stream - Video and still pictures
11. Transfer of OSC to Coastal Administration	The OSC role is transferred to the Coastal Administration when the SAR activity is completed. The Coastal Administration is responsible for pollution clean-up operations: planning; monitoring; assessment; replanning; status
12. Coordination	Cross—Border incident data information, data shared and coordination between the response assets. Request of assistance to the incident; incident position; type of required assets;
13. Engage Air Support	Air support for monitoring pollution - Telemetry: Drone flight status + drone path - Mission data: sensor data streams - Video and still pictures
14. Air Mission Data	- Sensor data streams - Video and still pictures
15. Initiate clean-up	Use available equipment and assets to clean up the pollution

INFO FLOW	DESCRIPTION
16. Result of clean-up	Status and result of the clean-up operation is reported back to the OSC.
17. Incident Report (NO/SE)	Data on cross-border confirmed incidents (NO/SE) + information request
18. Political Coordination	Countries authorization and political agreements

Table 8 - UC4 information flow (Source D2.3)

The following interaction scheme represents the actions and capabilities that will be implemented in use case 4.

Figure 33 - UC4: Interaction Diagram (Source D.2.3).

7 Evaluation Methodology

This chapter describes the basic principles for the evaluation methodology, which will be further developed in future deliverables (T.7.4 “Evaluation and validation”, D.7.3 “System Validation and Evaluation”) and will be followed for the evaluation of harmonisation opportunities that will be examined through the four exercise-trials.

7.1 Definition of the term “Evaluation”

The second major pillar, upon which T.7.1 is built, is the development of an evaluation framework and methodology, based on which the harmonisation opportunities are going to be assessed via the Testbed. For the development of this methodology, it is important to clarify what the term “evaluation” exactly means. According to ISO 22300 “evaluation is a systematic process that compares the result of measurement to recognized criteria to determine the discrepancies between intended and actual performance”. Practically **the evaluation is the means to identify if a system, a tool, a procedure or players’ performance has achieved predefined objectives or not**. With the evaluation the benefits of the, under examination, system or procedure, are assessed. Through the evaluation end users have the capability to check if and to what extent their work and operations are facilitated by the introduction of a novel technology or procedure, if and how much response times are reduced and to what extent their overall capacity is enhanced.

In order to effectively conduct an evaluation, some preliminary work has to be done prior to the evaluation itself. This means that specific attention has to be paid in the preparation and planning phase of the exercise. During the planning phase the scope of the exercise and its main objectives need to be defined. Specific criteria and Key Performance Indicators need to be set beforehand, with the aim to measure the objectives so that, through the evaluation, critical conclusions about the exercise and the under-examination solution (tool, procedure etc.) can be drawn. These objectives need to be clearly defined and to be as specific as possible, otherwise the process of assessment of the actual against the desired results might be hindered. The SMART methodology is a useful tool for the development of such objectives that will reflect targeted capabilities, which are being tested through the exercise. The SMART methodology defines five aspects that the objectives need to fulfil:

- The objectives need to be **Specific** and therefore, even if an objective is quite complex, it has to be divided in more and simpler subobjectives.
- The objectives need to be **Measurable** using quantitative criteria for their characterisation.
- The objectives need to be **Achievable** taking into consideration limitations and constraints not only of the exercise but also of the participants.
- The objectives need to be **Relevant** i.e., related to the goals of the exercise and the targeted capabilities of the participating organizations and, additionally, **Realistic**, thus not exceeding what is expected to be achieved through the exercise.
- The objectives need to be **Time-bound** i.e., to be met within a specific timespan, and, moreover, to be **Task-oriented**.

Taking the above into account, the formation of a team that is responsible for the planning, development and implementation of an *Evaluation Guide* is advised, coordinated by the Evaluation Lead. This guide is a tool for the evaluators, which highlights the objectives that need to be met, targets tested in the context of the exercise, and it provides guidance on how to collect relevant data and information in order to assess the results. In operational exercises, an

evaluation plan is also entailed, a document that provides the evaluators with instructions on how to conduct the evaluation. For the case of the exercise-trial, in which procedures need to be more simplified, the evaluation methodology other than being clearly documented, can be communicated to exercise-participants during preparatory meetings. During the latter, the role of each participant in the evaluation is described.

The evaluation spans across all phases of the exercise:

- The **preparation**, with preparation of the documentation, the set-up of data collection means (e.g., video cameras, audio recordings, etc.), the explanation of the evaluation scope and method to exercise participants
- The **conduct**, during which data collection takes place. This is composed by documentation of the observations by the evaluators and observers, the data registration via other means (recordings, log files, etc.), communication of participants experience during debriefing meetings or interviews
- The **review phase**, during which the players populate and submit their input via the participant feedback form, and the compilation and analysis of data takes place by the evaluation and exercise managing teams. Comparison of performance with key performance indicators, in quantitative or qualitative terms, takes place. Main conclusions are drawn and documented.

Although the input of internal and external evaluators is the most significant for evaluation in operational exercises, in the case of exercise-trials, data on the evaluation of the solution tested is primarily collected by the players who make use of the tools and have the chance to transfer the hands-on experience. Nevertheless, the observations of the evaluators (and observers if selected to be engaged also as evaluators) are of great importance and they are requested on two dimensions:

- The interaction of the players with and within the solutions
- The exercise planning and conduct itself (logistics, resources, etc.) for improvement purposes of the organizational aspects

Through the evaluation two major conclusions are drawn:

1. **Strengths**, i.e., aspects that were tested and operated well throughout the exercise, or activities with better results than the ones expected.
2. **Weaknesses**, i.e., areas, which need further improvement and therefore, they need to be translated into a comprehensive action plan for solutions' improvement and/or, following the performance objectives.

Usually, strengths are not equally weighed as weaknesses, but they are equally significant, nonetheless, as the strong aspects of tools and processes of crisis management should not be overlooked as further capabilities may be built on top of them.

Any recommendation to address possible weakness of the solutions tested or of the exercise conduct are registered, as they consist of significant ideas for updates and improvement.

7.2 Definition of the terms “Verification” and “Validation”

First responders' organisations use different terms to describe the end user driven and the technical evaluation. The IEEE 1012-2016 standard provides accurate definitions of the terms “validation” and “verification”. According to this standard **“validation is the process of evaluating a system or component during or at the end of the development process to**

determine whether it satisfies specified requirements. The process of providing evidence that the system, software or hardware and its associated products satisfy requirements allocated to it at the end of each life cycle activity, solve the right problem (e.g., correctly model physical laws, implement business rules and use the proper system assumptions), **and satisfy intended use and user needs.**" In other words, validation is the activity that ensures that an end product meets the expectations and needs of end users. On the other hand, "**verification is the process of evaluating a system or component to determine whether the products of a given development phase satisfy the conditions imposed at the start of that phase. The process of providing objective evidence that the system, software or hardware and its associated products conform to requirements** (e.g., for correctness, completeness, consistency and accuracy) for all life cycle activities during each life cycle process (acquisition, supply, development, operation and maintenance); **satisfy standards, practices and conventions** during life cycle processes and successfully complete each life cycle activity **and satisfy all the criteria for initiating succeeding life cycle activities.** Verification of interim work products is essential for proper understanding and assessment of the life cycle phase product(s)." In other words, verification takes place during the test of a system so as to prove that it meets all specified technical requirements at a particular stage of its development." According to the aforementioned IEEE standard "Life cycle processes or activities are defined as "the set of interrelated or interacting activities that result in the development or assessment of system, software or hardware products. Each activity consists of tasks. The life cycle processes may overlap one another. For verification and validation purposes, no life cycle process is concluded until its development products are verified and validated according to the defined the verification and validation plan."

Considering the above definitions, the validation of a system is related to its assessment by the end users' perspective, focusing to the satisfaction of key performance indicators set by end users as well as the usability of tested solutions, whereas the verification is connected to the technical assessment against its initially set specifications aiming to the verification that the solution (that will be tested later by end-users) operates properly. It is very essential, not only in the context of D.7.1, but also for the whole project to use this standardised terminology.

In an exercise-trial, **evaluation has to be both end user driven and technically oriented.** End users are considered the first responders in the context of the Valkyries project, as it is related to disaster management and more specifically to first aid response. First responders are the final recipients, and the development of novel solutions is specifically designed to address their operational needs. Therefore, their point of view is of utmost importance to assess whether or not a solution has practical value. On the other hand, when a technological solution is evaluated, its technical specifications have to be taken into consideration. Specific metrics should be developed prior to the execution of the exercise-trial addressing the already set objectives and, throughout the implementation of the exercise, relevant data have to be collected for the final assessment. This technically directed evaluation is performed mainly by the technological developers of the under-examination solution(s). In particular, when it comes to the implementation and testing of several interoperable components integrated to a unique platform, technological providers should organise and perform preliminary tests in a controlled environment, with the aim to ensure that all subsystems are working, not only individually but also as a whole, and effectively communicating with each other. For this purpose, technical and operational harmonisation needs to have been achieved during the development and preparation phase of the exercise-trial and its successful implementation will be evaluated initially during the verification and then the validation phase. Verification is conducted mainly

by the producers of the system(s), thus comprising an internal process, whereas validation, which is conducted by end users is an external process. Verification provides feedback related to the appropriate architecture of the system and is conducted, as already mentioned above, even before the exercise-trial. Validation ensures acceptance of the system by the users, thus ensuring that the tested system is the appropriate solution for them.

7.3 Verification and Validation general flow

The Valkyries Verification and Validation Plan is integrated into its Test Plan and includes a multistage process in which the Valkyries Consortium and the end users will work iteratively or in concurrence (the latter, if the nature and dependencies of the tests to be carried out allow it) towards specifying results that functionally meet the harmonisation opportunities set, which support the contrast of the research hypothesis, while satisfying the user's expectations. Based on the considerations mentioned throughout this document, the Valkyries Consortium has proposed the following plan of evaluation activities.

Phase	Name	Description	Main Actors
1	Definition of success criteria	The VALKYRIES Consortium will identify and elaborate a list of performance indicators that serve as a threshold for assessing the success of each test to be carried out. Based on a legend scheme, the different levels of performance in each test (from "excellent" to "insufficient") will be defined.	Valkyries Consortium
2	Success Criteria Agreement	The performance indicators will be reviewed and agreed by the contracting party and its end users, agreeing with the VALKYRIES Consortium any comments, additional conditions, or proposed amendments.	Valkyries Consortium EC
3	Verification tests on harmonisation opportunities	The VALKYRIES Consortium will execute the verification tests, collect the evidence of its results and proceed to its documentation. In addition, to support the design and implementation phase, alternative tests may be carried out initially not described in this document, ; also proceeding to the documentation of the same. The latter will not require direct traceability with the objectives of the Project, serving as support for specific situations. Therefore, they will not be part of the verification process itself, although they will be able to contribute to the validation of the results.	Valkyries Consortium
4	Modular validation	The contractor and the end users involved shall complete the validation questionnaires associated with the results of each level of testing.	Valkyries Consortium EC
5	Project validation	The contractor and the end users involved will proceed to complete the validation	Valkyries Consortium EC

Phase	Name	Description	Main Actors
		questionnaires associated with the overall result of the Project.	
6	Retrospective analysis, lessons learned and conclusions	Scope analysis on the strengths, weaknesses and opportunities of the hypotheses made in the design stages and their fulfilment. Conclusions and lessons learned about the work done. Guidelines and recommendations to guide future related work, as well as the possible technological evolution of the results.	Valkyries Consortium
7	Documentation	The processes followed and results achieved during the execution of the plan will be formally documented.	Valkyries Consortium

Table 9 - Verification and Validation Plan

Overall, the evaluation procedures are initiated since the first preliminary test. At this stage of **verification of the harmonisation opportunities**, the interoperable performance of the solution needs to be tested against specific key performance indicators with technical metrics, identified and defined exclusively by solution providers. It is taken for granted that the successful operation of individual solutions, data exchange and communication is fundamental for the performance of the system. In case of technical failures and need for slight modifications of the solutions, the integrated system or the Testbed platform, more than one preliminary test may be needed.

Main participants in this process are the technological providers, but also the technically competent end users e.g., first responders, are advised to be present as observers, in order to have a generic overview of the system and the way it will be implemented during the exercise-trials deployment.

During the exercise-trial, the players, who will mainly be the first responders, will provide their input via the Participant Feedback Form, which has the form of a questionnaire with close- and open-ended questions divided in two main sections: (a) evaluation of the exercise planning and conduct, and (b) validation of the solutions i.e., harmonisation opportunities, from the end-user perspective. The close-ended questions can have binary (yes/no) or trinary (yes/no/partially) answers or they can be rating answers using for example the Likert-scale. Moreover, open-ended questions allow respondents to expand more on their expectations and observations and to highlight aspects they consider important for future improvements. Although quantifiable responses can be better analysed, qualitative answers are equally valuable. For each criterion of the solutions performance that needs validation, a combination of a quantitative and qualitative answer is advisable, as well as questioning the same aspect with different approaches and perspectives.

The following schema provides the flow of the verification and validation procedures for the technological harmonisation opportunities to be assessed through the use cases.

7.3.1 Verification of the harmonisation opportunities

As already described above, **verification is the technical evaluation of a technological solution while it is being developed**. It focuses on technical specifications and is mainly conducted by the technological provider(s), who has/have the overall picture of the system. For the verification of a system several rehearsals and preliminary tests have to be undertaken with the aim to check that the solution performs in an acceptable manner. The number of these tests may vary considering possible issues that may arise throughout their execution, or the number of subsystems, which have to be interconnected and communicate with each other.

During its execution the system should be tested in a simulated environment but with conditions as realistic as possible, as if it were the actual trial. At this stage a variety of issues has to be addressed, e.g., the data collection plan to be implemented during the execution of the preliminary test, as well as, the criteria, which will be used for the verification of the under-examination system. In the case that interoperability or other issues have been identified the organisation of a follow-up test is advisable. The aim of a second test is to address all issues to maximise the functionality of the system.

Technological providers have to define verification metrics and specific KPIs to be measured during the tests which are related to the technical performance of the system. Moreover, first responders, as end users of the solution, are not excluded from this procedure, as they can provide further feedback, should they have technical experience.

In the following chapters an in-depth analysis of how the verification methodology should be conducted is presented.

Equipment and ICT enablers for First Aid Response harmonisation opportunities (WP4)

In the scope of WP4 “Equipment and ICT enablers for First Aid Responses”, and specifically of D4.2 “Harmonisation opportunities on the technological landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters” an identification of opportunities for harmonisation will take place. From the set of harmonisation opportunities, the most feasible and representative ones will be selected. These harmonisation opportunities may vary throughout the project lifecycle due to the nature and breadth of the set of technologies used by first aid responders as well as the ongoing process of discovering and evaluating harmonisation alternatives.

For each harmonisation opportunity, the following information should be provided to allow the best method for the verification and validation to be considered:

- **Description:** Account of the scope of the opportunity for harmonisation and justification.
- **Considerations:** context in which this harmonisation opportunity must be contemplated and factors to be considered so that this opportunity is sustainable, replicable, and reusable.
- **Level:** Priority suggested by the D4.3 Roadmap deliverable for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters.

Here there are some potential examples:

Valkyries Harmonisation opportunity – HO-4-1	
Title	
Description	
Considerations	
Level	

Valkyries Harmonisation opportunity – HO-4-2	
Title	
Description	
Considerations	
Level	

Table 10 – WP4 Harmonization opportunity potential tables

Common Practices and operational procedures for First Aid Responses harmonization opportunities (WP5)

In the scope of WP5 Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responses, specifically, the D5.2 Harmonisation opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters there is an identification of opportunities for harmonisation. From the set of harmonisation opportunities, the feasible and representative set

of being able to address their validation and verification plan will be selected. These harmonisation opportunities may vary throughout the project lifecycle due to the nature and breadth of the set of technologies used by first aid responders as well as the ongoing process of discovering and evaluating harmonization alternatives.

For each harmonisation opportunity, the following information should be provided to allow the best method of evaluation and validation to be considered:

- **Description:** Account of the scope of the opportunity for harmonisation and justification.
- **Considerations:** context in which this harmonisation opportunity must be contemplated and factors to be considered so that this opportunity is sustainable, replicable, and reusable.
- **Level:** Priority suggested by the D5.3 Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European operational and procedural capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters.

Here there are some potential examples:

Valkyries Harmonisation opportunity – HO-5-1	
Title	
Description	
Considerations	
Level	

Valkyries Harmonisation opportunity – HO-5-2	
Title	
Description	
Considerations	
Level	

Table 11 – WP5 Harmonization opportunity potential tables

Cooperation, Education and Training for First Aid Responses (WP6)

In the scope of WP6 Cooperation, Education and Training for First Aid Responses, specifically, the D.6.2 Harmonisation opportunities on the preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters there is an identification of opportunities for harmonisation. From the set of harmonisation opportunities, the feasible and representative set of being able to address their validation and verification plan will be selected. These harmonisation opportunities may vary throughout the project lifecycle due to the nature and breadth of the set of technologies used by first aid responders as well as the ongoing process of discovering and evaluating harmonisation alternatives.

For each harmonisation opportunity, the following information should be provided to allow the best method of evaluation and validation to be considered:

- **Description:** Account of the scope of the opportunity for harmonisation and justification.
- **Considerations:** context in which this harmonisation opportunity must be contemplated and factors to be considered so that this opportunity is sustainable, replicable, and reusable.

- **Level:** Priority suggested by the D6.3 Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters.

Here there are some potential examples:

Valkyries Harmonisation opportunity – HO-6-1	
Title	
Description	
Considerations	
Level	

Valkyries Harmonisation opportunity – HO-6-2	
Title	
Description	
Considerations	
Level	

Table 12 – WP6 Harmonization opportunity potential tables

7.3.2 Qualification Methods for Verification

The verification process will focus on use cases, which will cover their test cases, Valkyries prototyping, if applicable, the structured tests associated with each of them, their data flows, and the visual support material (diagrams, schematics, visual analysis, etc.) to their design, implementation, execution, and reasoning on the observed results. The following are the methods to be used during the verification and validation of the project results:

Requirements Engineering is an extensive technological field which influences present document. Nevertheless, defining and describing Requirements Engineering is beyond the scope of this document. In Product Engineering, Product Verification, among other things, is a contractual and legal set of procedures, checks and meetings. A successful Product Verification assures the Product adheres to the Contractual Product Requirements. Such process is done through a battery of Product Requirements Verification, through contractually accorded tests. Tests are, in general, are classified into several categories:

- **Demonstration (D):** verifies the operation of the system or a part of the system, based on an observable functional operation that does not require the use of instrumentation, special test equipment or subsequent analysis.
Demo verification means that the product or system being evaluated behaves as it should. Therefore, the person(s), appointed to technically verify the solutions, can follow the functional harmonisation opportunities described and verify that the evaluation object behaves as specified. In the case of software solutions, testers often enter the information just as users will, making sure the software performs the actions it is supposed to and checking that their reports are correct.
- **Test (T):** verifies the operation of the system or a part of the system based on the use of instruments or other special test equipment to collect data for further analysis. Test execution is technically the most accurate and controlled process of verifying a capability. Based on this, technical experts can confirm that a functionality operates as expected contextualised in a series of specifications, pre-conditions, and post-condition expectations. Tests are typically repeated by alternating different configuration

parameters and input data, tracing step by step their feed flow and observable intermediate results. Valkyries preliminarily considers the execution of at least four types of tests:

- *Unit tests*. Verifications supported by specific software that allows to automate that the execution of functionalities of the system to be evaluated result in the expected results previously defined.
- *Integration test*. Verifications to be carried out in the field of software development once the unit tests have been approved, evaluating that all the unitary elements that make up the software work together correctly operating in a group.
- *Reliability test*. Tests focused on evaluating the reliability of the functions to be verified, given the environmental conditions, and for a certain time.
- *Security test*. Tests aimed at evaluating the level of vulnerability and risk in the different attack surfaces present in the functionalities to be verified.
- **Analysis (A)**: verifies the processing of accumulated data obtained by other qualification methods. Examples include the reduction, interpolation, or extrapolation of test results. Verification by Analysis is applied in place of, or in addition to, test and demo checks to verify compliance with specific harmonisation opportunities. Selected techniques may include system engineering analysis, statistics and qualitative analysis, computer analysis and simulations; typically relying on benchmarks and collections of reference results. It is applied in the verification actions in which the Valkyries Consortium determines that:
 - Rigorous and accurate analysis is possible.
 - Test ratings are neither feasible nor profitable.
 - Similarity (acceptance by previously accepted similar results) is not applicable.
 - Inspection Verification is not adequate
- **Inspection (I)**: visual examination of system components, documentation, etc. Inspection is the examination of the product or system using basic senses, so that they are physically examined based on their required physical characteristics and the control mechanisms they are supposed to present. Similarly, in the case of a software system, testers must check that its user interface is as required, presenting all the fields and data entry buttons it is supposed to have, etc. In the context of Valkyries, a thorough documentary inspection of the results of the Project will be carried out throughout its product life cycle, in which the evaluators will be able to constantly provide information, assessments and, when required, the approval of the Consortium's decisions. These documentary inspections shall be complemented by a direct human inspection of the capabilities delivered, mainly targeting user interfaces and related user-friendly information sources. Regarding the inspection of codes and software, human evaluation measures will be supported by third-party instruments deployed in the development environment and on the test benches (Virtual Laboratory), which will automatically facilitate the discovery of inconsistencies, errors, missing fields, etc. Software-guided inspection will adopt the described contractually agreed capabilities, allowing for the modular integration of related and specific third-party solutions where necessary. These capabilities will also support the Continuous Integration (CI) process. The Virtual Lab will provide the necessary development kit for programmers, designers, evaluators, and any other user profile that potentially engages in the daily inspection of the results produced.

- **Special qualification methods (S)**: cover any special qualification method for the system, such as tools, techniques, procedures, facilities, acceptance limits, use of standard samples, pre-production or periodic production samples, pilot models or pilot batches; not collected in the above methods.

Each verification procedure in Valkyries describes three measurable indicators (either quantitatively or qualitatively) on which compliance with at least one requirement is based. The test plan shall adopt three categories:

- **Effectiveness measures (EM)**, i.e., measures of mission success from the point of view of stakeholders.
- **Performance measures (PM)** are used to determine whether the system meets the performance indicators needed to meet the EMs.
- Parameters or **key performance indicators (KPIs)** defined by stakeholders as measures of the minimum and critical performance of the system or process, as well as its level of acceptance.

Each verification test will receive an assessment based on the following legend:

- **A**: Successful verification. Excellent results were observed (the best possible performance was observed)
- **B**: Successful verification. Outstanding results (very good performance) were observed
- **C**: Successful verification. The results are in line with expectations. Average approval.
- **D**: Successful verification. There is a wide range of improvements to be considered in future work. Conditionally approved. Minimum degree of approval.
- **E**: Verification failed. The minimum verification conditions have not been exceeded

7.3.3 Validation of the harmonisation opportunities

Validation processes take place during the conduct of the trial-exercise as data collection apparently runs in parallel to its execution. Valkyries validation actions are carried out at two levels during the conduct and review phase of the exercise-trials developed to support the use case requirements.

1. **Individual validation of results by objective.** The end user will validate and indicate their level of acceptance by objective, being the functionalities that lead to its fulfilment. Considering that Valkyries addresses a novel research action and beyond the state of the art, in addition to the mere validation of project results, this is also expected to lay the groundwork for other related research/development activities, pointing out the pros and cons, lessons learned, elements of controversy, and other materials that serve in future considerations.
2. **General validation of Valkyries.** End users will validate and report their degree of acceptance of Valkyries results. Like individual component validation, this will also signal reactions to encourage and guide future research/development.

The exercise-trials will be executed step by step and the observations will be preserved to be contrasted with the expected results. During the exercise-trials, the harmonised opportunities will be tested as a "solution" and the observed and recorded results will be compared against expected results. If the actual results match the expected results for each test case, the case study will be "validated". If the number of unapproved test cases is less than the project's default threshold, the test suite is "approved." If it is larger, the system can be rejected or accepted

under conditions previously agreed by the Technical Team of the Project and the end users. The expected result of a successful test run follows the following dynamics:

1. The test cases are executed, using default data
2. Actual results are recorded
3. Actual and expected results are compared
4. The results of the test are determined

The objective is to provide confidence that the validation object meets the minimum functional and non-functional conditions necessary in the framework of each study, as to consider the perspective of the end user (with a view to its acceptance by validation). Once completed, and provided that the acceptance criteria are met, end users are expected to provide feedback on product development/improvement as satisfactory to the defined harmonization opportunities; this action will allow non-functional performance indicators to be evaluated.

During the validation of a solution, the influence the solution has on first responders' operations is assessed, as well as its added value to disaster management in general. The process of validation is undertaken mainly by the players of the exercise, taking into account that they have a close interaction with the tested solution and thus, are the ones whose opinions have most significance regarding the solution, its strengths and potential areas needing further improvement. However, also observers and evaluator(s) can express their opinions in dedicated questionnaires. First responders are expected to provide input regarding the improvements, that the tested tool or ensemble of tools brings to their operations, operational needs, which are facilitated and improved with the use of the tool, factors that lead to the adoption and successful implementation of the tool by first responders' organisations, areas that need improvement and potential constraints that have been identified, recommendations on how to overcome these barriers and potential additional functionalities, that the first responders would like to see in the future along with possible ethical issues that may arise from the use of the tool. Therefore, it is advisable that the trial should run twice, once without the solution and once with the solution with the aim the validation process to provide concrete and robust feedback related to potential changes the solution brings.

The most crucial aspect needed to be validated by the end users is the usability of the under-examination solution. According to ISO/IEC 25060:2010, the **usability** of a solution is examined under three perspectives, effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction.

- **Effectiveness** describes the convenience or difficulty of the end user to achieve specific goals with the use of the tested solution.
- **Efficiency** is the extent, to which the uptake of a new solution for the achievement of goals and objectives minimises the use and deployment of resources.
- **Satisfaction** is the extent to which the proposed solution covers end users' requirements.

For all three perspectives of usability, specific metrics have to be identified and measured through questions addressed mainly to players in dedicated questionnaires. Through these questions the validation of the solution can be conducted and several aspects can be scrutinized:

- The level of difficulty in understanding the objectives achieved through the use of the solution

- The extent, to which the number of needed resources is reduced through the use of the novel solution
- Reduction of response times
- Easiness of use
- The level of technical and/or scientific competence the user has to have in order to use the solution
- The complexity of the solution
- The level of adequacy of end users' training to the use of the solution prior to the exercise conduct
- The potential of adoption of the solution by first responders' organizations
- The extent, to which the solution can be actuated under different circumstances and conditions
- The level of enhancement of first responders' capabilities that is brought by the implementation of the solution
- The level, to which the use of the solution facilitates decision making and provides situational awareness and a common operational picture for all stakeholders
- The overall extent, to which the solution covered end users' needs

The above questions should be answered in a quantifiable manner, but also the end users' opinions and feedback are essential. Thus, open ended questions for their inputs regarding strengths, weaknesses, recommendations, improvements they would like to see in potential future versions of the solution and their general comments for the solution and the overall exercise should be included in the questionnaire.

Moreover, technical aspects of the system have to be inspected also by the end users. Although the check against technical characteristics appertain to the verification procedure, which follows the conclusion of the preliminary tests, first responders, who have the expertise to provide a technologically oriented perspective, are advised to give their feedback regarding the functionality and operational capacity of the system itself, apart from the influence it has on operational activities. The following criteria are indicative and could be used as a basis for the formation of the aforementioned questionnaire:

- Ease of installation of the solution (time required for the installation, complexity of installation, dependency to other systems (hardware or software))
- Scalability, extensibility and compatibility with already existing solutions which are already used by first responders
- Reliability, and security of the system for the processing of data
- Assessment of the online services
- Level of integration and consistency of the different components in the system

On the other hand, evaluator(s) and/or observers of the exercise might be asked for more generic feedback, which will be focused more on their perception and impression of the interaction the end users had with the tested solution and their overall satisfaction. Additionally, other aspects could be investigated in this questionnaire related to the affordability of the solution, its credibility, the added value the solution brings to disaster management, the level of innovation. Some questions in the players' questionnaire might also be included in the evaluators' questionnaire e.g., ease of use, potential adoption of the solution by the end users' organizations and the extent of facilitation of operations with the use of the newly introduced solution among others. What is important is to validate and also verify improvements in the

performance of the Testbed between the exercises. For the verification part this will be done also at the preliminary tests stage, but in terms of validation this will take place at the use case deployment stage.

Indicative examples of questionnaires related to the end users' validation of the harmonisation opportunities, with questions related to the usability of the system, the easiness of use, terminological issues and the overall satisfaction and acceptance of the opportunity by end users is provided in Annex A. In addition, in Annex B, questions that can be included in the second, more technically oriented, questionnaire, addressed to the end users, are presented. Finally, in Annex C, an indicative reporting sheet, in which the verification results of the technological harmonisation opportunities are depicted, is presented.

7.4 Evaluation criteria for achieving interoperability

One very important aspect that has to be examined through the exercise-trials is interoperability. According to ISO 22300:2021 interoperability is “**the ability of diverse systems and organisations to work together**”, while the European Commission defines the term as “**the ability of organisations to interact towards mutually beneficial goals, involving the sharing of information and knowledge between these organisations, through the business processes they support, by means of the exchange of data between their ICT systems**”³. Interoperability is the core focus of the Valkyries project taking into consideration that it aims at the identification of harmonisation opportunities, and by this is meant equipment and ICT, operational procedures and practices, and cooperation, education and training frameworks, to be widely adopted and used by first responders' organisations for a coordinated and effective first aid response in multi casualty incidents. Therefore, interoperability is a basic criterion to be examined and evaluated through the exercise-trials.

According to the European Interoperability Framework, interoperability can be clustered in four basic pillars i.e., legal, organisational, semantic, technical interoperability, all of which lead to the fifth category i.e., an integrated public service governance. In the context of the Valkyries project all four levels are of equal importance.

For the **technical interoperability aspect**, it is already mentioned that mainly technological providers have to verify that the different modules of the system have to be interconnected and effectively communicating with each other. This verification procedure will take place in the preliminary technological tests, which will be executed prior to the actual exercise-trials conduct (chapter 7.3). These preliminary tests are conducted to examine interface specifications, efficiency in data exchange between the interconnected systems and secure communication protocols.

Moreover, taking into consideration that also operational harmonisation opportunities will be explored through the system, also interorganisational cooperation and effectiveness will be examined. Interoperability between different organisations is of utmost importance in operations requiring the collaboration of several parties.

Legal interoperability ensures that the legal framework applied to different organisations within or among EU Member States does not prohibit collaboration and exchange of data and information between them. Therefore, fragmentation of legal framework among member states and nations, that is a serious emerging problem, can be a topic for discussion. Furthermore, legal

³ https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/sites/default/files/eif_brochure_final.pdf

interoperability can facilitate technological development, with technological innovations being adopted and used without legal restrictions.

Organisational interoperability, a crucial aspect in disaster management in general, is according to the EIF “the way in which public administrations align their business processes, responsibilities and expectations to achieve commonly agreed and mutually beneficial goals”. Harmonisation opportunities related to both operational and training and collaboration procedures have to be validated against this exact aspect. Widely adopted operational plans and protocols lead to harmonised disaster response, to effective cross-sector collaboration, when different agencies to manage a disaster are demanded, and, most importantly to cross-border efficiency. It is apparent that the evaluator(s) of the use cases have to thoroughly examine the level of interoperability that is introduced by the operational harmonisation opportunities, which will be implemented in the exercise-trials.

Semantic interoperability is essential that end users interpret data and information exchanged through the systems that will be integrated to the system in the same way. This semantic interpretation of data is a crucial factor for the end user driven validation of the Testbed.

The evaluation of the harmonisation opportunities can be related to the abovementioned pillars, considering that main scope of Valkyries is to identify technical, operational, cooperation and training opportunities that will allow for high level interoperability among first aid organisations.

8 Conclusions

Through this document the development of two of the most vital components of the Valkyries project are described: a) the development of the Testbed and the system, through which the harmonisation opportunities that will be identified in the context of WP4, WP5 and WP6, will be examined against their potential to be widely adopted and used by end users in first aid response and b) the evaluation methodology, which will be followed in order to identify the level of acceptance of these opportunities by the first responders' community.

The modules and services of the system are delineated. At this stage of the project, the system will consist of a communications module, which will allow machine to machine communications, and of an audit module which is used for the collection and storage of all information exchanged during the execution of the exercise-trials. However, taking into consideration the structure of the project, the integration of further modules provided by technical partners of the consortium cannot be excluded. The exact composition of the system and its components will be one of the core outcomes of Deliverable 7.3 "Reference Integration and harmonisations".

In order to outline the evaluation methodology, it was crucial to first provide an overview not only of the use cases but also of the overall process required to conduct an exercise. Due to the fact that harmonisation opportunities are going to be tested and implemented through the system, the use cases are renamed to exercise-trials. Furthermore, a brief overview of the four exercise-trials, the participants (real or simulated) and the interactions between them are provided. It was highly essential to depict the link shared between the exercise-trials, the development of the system and the evaluation methodology that will be followed. The description of the exercise-trials (deliverable D2.3) has been reviewed and further elaborated.

Finally, the evaluation methodology is significantly elaborated. The core point of the evaluation process is the division between the technical verification and the end user validation. Verification procedures examine specific technical characteristics and the technical performance of the system and its units, whereas the validation process examines the solutions in terms of effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction, thus in terms of their overall acceptance by end users. Yet, apart from the generic validation of the system, also an end user driven technological validation takes place, although without diving deep into technical details. Verification methods ([chapter 7.3.2](#)) as well as indicative criteria for the end user validation ([chapter 7.3.3](#)) are provided in this document. These criteria are practically topic which will lay the basis for the full formation of the KPIs and the questionnaires, to be used in the exercise-trials, in the framework of T.7.4 "Evaluation and validation".

9 Annex A - References and bibliography

1. Active Integrated Matter, “AIM’s Research Test beds”, <https://research.csiro.au/aim/home/aims-research-test-beds/>
2. CEN Workshop Agreement 17514:2020 “Systematic Assessment of Innovative Solutions for Crisis Management – Trial Guidance Methodology”, 2020, https://www.cenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/CWAs/RI/cwa17514_2020.pdf
3. D2.1: “Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases”
4. D2.3: “Architecture Design Document”
5. Driver+, “Trial Guidance Methodology Handbook”, 2020, <https://www.driver-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/TGM-handbook-FINAL.pdf>
6. Fortier, P.; Michel, H. “Computer Systems Performance Evaluation and Prediction”, 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-55558-260-9.X5000-0>
7. IEEE 1012-2016, IEEE Standard for System, Software and Hardware Verification and Validation, 2016, <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/1012/5609/>
8. International Maritime Organization (IMO), IMO Publications and Documents, Maritime Safety Committee, MSC.1/Circular.1494, “Guidelines on Harmonization of Testbed Reporting”, 2014, <https://www.imorules.com/GUID-935BBA8C-2E7D-42B0-A6F8-354F06554FCE.html>
9. ISO 22300:2021, Societal security – Vocabulary, 2021, <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:22300:ed-3:v1:en>
10. ISO 22398:2013, Societal security – Guidelines for exercises, 2013, <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:22398:ed-1:v1:en>
11. ISO/IEC 25060:2010, Systems and software engineering – Systems and software product Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuARE) – Common Industry Format (CIF) for usability: General framework for usability-related information, 2010, <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso-iec:tr:25060:ed-1:v1:en>
12. Pospisil, O.; Blazek, P.; Kuchar K.; Fujdiak, R.; Misurec, J. “Application Perspective on Cybersecurity Testbed for Industrial Control Systems” *Sensors*, 2021, 21, 8119. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21238119>
13. The European Commission, “New European Interoperability Framework”, 2017, https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/sites/isa/files/eif_brochure_final.pdf
14. US Department of Homeland Security, *Homeland Security Exercise and Evaluation Program (HSEEP)*, 2020, <https://www.fema.gov/sites/default/files/2020-04/Homeland-Security-Exercise-and-Evaluation-Program-Doctrine-2020-Revision-2-2-25.pdf>

10 Annex B - Glossary

Acronym	Description
AKS	Azure Kubernetes Service
EC	The European Commission
ELK	Elastic + Logstash + Kibana
EU	The European Union
EUCPM	The European Union Civil Protection Mechanism
SAR	Search and Rescue
C2	Command and Control
CP	Civil Protection
CP Operation	Civil Protection Operation
CD	Continuous Deployment / Delivery
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
GIS	Geographical Information Systems
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Code
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MiTM	Man in the Middle
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NTP	Network Time Protocol
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
POI	Point of Interest
SaaS	Service as a Code
SpO2	Oxygen level in blood
VPN	Virtual Private Network

Table 13 - Glossary

11 Annex C – Indicative Questionnaires for Validation

Questions to the end user about [XXX] Harmonisation Opportunity		Assessment						
		1	2	3	4	5	N/A	details
Usability								
U1	Using [XXX] would allow me to carry out tasks more quickly and effectively							
U2	Using [XXX] facilitates operations and reduces response time							
U3	The use of [XXX] reduces the deployment of other resources during an operation							
U4	I find [XXX] useful in my work							
Ease of Use								
E1	My interaction with [XXX] is clear, understandable, and intuitive.							
E2	I can say that my interaction with [XXX] is agile and flexible							
E3	It's easy for me to become skilled at using [XXX]							
System Terminology and Information								
T1	I consider the use of the terms to be appropriate							
T2	I find appropriate the terminology related to training plans							
T3	The adjustment parameters and their explanations are understandable							
T4	Alerts and issues issued are properly emphasized							
Satisfaction								
S1	I am satisfied with [XXX]							
S2	I would recommend [XXX] to my team							
S3	Using [XXX] makes my job easier							
S4	I felt very confident using [XXX]							

Table 14 – Indicative questionnaires for validation

12 Annex D – Indicative Questionnaire for the End User Technical Validation

Questions to the end user about [XXX] Harmonisation Opportunity		Assessment						
		1	2	3	4	5	N/A	details
Functionality								
F1	[XXX] is compatible with other systems operated by my organisation							
F2	The processing of data through the [XXX] is reliable and secure.							
F3	The [XXX] enables the integration of further modules and services							
F4	The installation of [XXX] is not time consuming							
F5	I am satisfied by the online services of [XXX]							
F6	Messages/prompts on the screen are understandable							
F7	[XXX] informs about its internal processes in a non-intrusive manner and as requested							

Table 15 – Indicative questionnaire for the end user technical validation

13 Annex E - Indicative Table for the Results of Verification Tests

Harmonisation Opportunity #ID to verify			
Description	Scope and coverage of the harmonisation opportunity (HO)		
Traceability	Traceability of the HO with respect to the tests carried out		
EM	PM	KPI	Verification method
<i>Error rate (%), etc.</i>	<i>Milliseconds, CPU usage (%)</i>	<i>False positives, accuracy, variability, etc.</i>	<i>Inspection, analysis, etc.</i>
Verification action #1	Description	<i>Description of the action and its context. It includes premises, expected results, etc.</i>	
	Execution	<i>Step-by-step description of how the verification test was run.</i>	
	Analysis and results	<i>Description of the procedure for collecting results, its analytical actions (if necessary) and the general results achieved.</i>	
	History of corrective measures	<i>If the verification initially failed, this cell describes the different corrective actions to fit expectations.</i>	
	Lessons learned	<i>It highlights the difficulties suffered, and any possible conclusions or lessons learned to be considered in the later stages of development.</i>	
	Quality	<i>Functional score of the verification action [A, B, C, D, E]. The legend of the score varies depending on the element to be validated, being declared for each test along with the quality thresholds to be considered, in Section Error! Reference source not found.</i>	
	End-user feedback	<i>Any comments highlighted by the end users of the Project during the verification process.</i>	
	Result	<i>YES/NO. Did you pass the test successfully? The achievement criteria require compliance with the verification (Quality Rating) and validation (Acceptance) criteria in accordance with the thresholds indicated in Section Error! Reference source not found.</i>	
Verification Action #2			
Verification action #n			

Table 16 – Indicative table for the results of verification tests